

LiDAR for Autonomous Vehicles

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Outline

- Autonomous Vehicles technology;
- Autonomous Vehicles structure;
- Environment perception;
- DARPA Grand Challenge;
 - Stanford/CMU/MIT/VT/Cornell;
- LiDAR;
- LiDAR calibration-other sensors;
- Hand eye calibration;
- LiDAR fusion-other sensors;
- LiDAR-based lane detection;
- LiDAR-based free space detection;
- LiDAR-based road sign detection;
- LiDAR-based traffic light detection;
- LiDAR-based obstacle detection;
- LiDAR-based tracking;
- LiDAR-based mapping;
- LiDAR-based localization;
- LiDAR-based segmentation;
- LiDAR-based scene parsing;
- LiDAR perception with DL;

Autonomous Vehicles' Technology

- Anti-Lock Brakes
- Electronic Stability control
- Adaptive cruise control
- Lane-departure warning system
- Self parking
- Automated guided vehicle systems
- Lidar-Systems or Cruise Automated Systems
- Infrared cameras.

Technology's Components

- Lane departure warning
 - Lazy or inattentive drivers can automatically be moved
- Blind spot monitoring
 - Warn if cars are in blind spots
- Pedestrian detection
 - Automatic brake or warning
- Adaptive cruise control + forward collision warning
 - Car stays a safe distance behind cars ahead of it
 - Warns or takes action in case of danger

General Structure of Autonomous Vehicles

Technology's Concept (Level 0~5)

Autonomous Vehicle Architecture

Environment Perception

Environment Perception

- **Localization-driven approaches:** Control the vehicle's pose in relation to a global coordinate system.
 - ❑ The map data is used to provide information about the stationary environment, especially about the course of the lanes.
 - ❑ Even more detailed maps are used to improve the host vehicle's global map-relative position due to insufficient availability of a precise GNSS-based localization.
- **Perception-driven approaches:** Perceive the complete environment with on-board sensors.
 - ❑ Camera data is fused with Lidar sensor data to determine accurate distances of relevant objects.

Environment Perception

Futura (Geddes, 1939)

Blocks World (Roberts, 1963)

- | | |
|-----------------------------|--|
| 1 Torque motor for steering | 6, 6 Transputer system, image processing |
| 2 brake system | 7 processors for gaze & locomotion control |
| 3 electric throttle control | 8 user interface |
| 4 front platform for 2 CCD | 9 linear accelerometers |
| 5 rear platform cameras | 10 angular rate sensors |

VaMP Car (Dickmanns, 1994)

Lane Detection (Aly, 2008)

Segmentation (Ess, 2009)

Road Detect. (Alvarez, 2010)

Intersection (Rasmussen, 2003)

Geom. Context (Hoiem, 2005)

Urban Challenge (Boss, 2007)

VIAC Challenge (Broggi, 2010)

Activity Recogn. (Wang, 2009)

Driverless Car (Google, 2011)

Environment Perception

Environment Perception

Environment Perception

- **Sensor data preprocessing**: fusion raw data for the sensors to provide info. on vehicle position and motion, obstacle and environment map;
- **Localization**: it establishes the correspondence between the car's present location, and the map;
- **Obstacle tracking**: tracking of static and moving objects;
- **Path planning**: Driving decisions are made using path planning method that determines one route that maximizes a plurality of criteria among multiple trajectories;
- **Behaviors**: a behavioral module that gradually relax constraints in the driving process to succeed in situations of unpredictable environments;
- **Control**: The final software component realizes control of the vehicle itself, its throttle, brake, gear shifter, and steering wheel.

Environment Fusion

Perception Driven Environment Modeling

Perception Driven Environment Modeling

(a) Tracked objects above reflectance layer

(b) Consistency layer overlay

(c) Classified stixel data

(a) Skeletonization

(b) Contour classification

(c) Final hypotheses

Perception Driven Environment Modeling

(b) Curb occupancy

(d) Reflectance data

(a) Elevated occupancy

(c) Ground visibility

(e) Fusion result

Fusion layer cell colors:

- Explicit free
- Implicit free
- Ground texture data
- Curbs
- Elevated occupancy
- Texture-elevated occupancy
- Multiple occupancy

Perception Driven Environment Modeling

(a) Road elements

(b) Lane center lines

(a) Tracking of opening lanes at inner-city intersections.

(b) Tracking of non-parallel lanes.

(c) Tracking of non-parallel lanes and opening lanes at inner-city intersections.

Stanley (Stanford U.)

(a)

(b)

○The main technological challenge was to build a highly reliable system, capable of driving at relatively high speeds through diverse and unstructured off-road environments, and to do all this with high precision.

□ Long-range **terrain perception**, real-time **collision avoidance**, and stable vehicle control on slippery and rugged terrain.

○It is 2004 **Volkswagen Touareg R5 TDI**, outfitted with a 6 processor computing platform (Intel), and a suite of sensors and actuators for autonomous driving;

○Driven by the speed requirement for the off-road driving field unsuitable;

○Algorithms from diverse areas including distributed systems, machine learning, and probabilistic robotics.

Stanley (Stanford U.)

- ❖ The Touareg has four-wheel drive 4WD, variable-height air suspension, and automatic electronic locking differentials;
- ❖ A custom interface enables direct electronic actuation of both throttle and brakes;
- ❖ A DC motor attached to the steering column provides **electronic steering control**;
- ❖ A linear actuator attached to the gear shifter shifts between drive, reverse, and parking gears;
- ❖ Vehicle data, i.e. individual wheel speeds and steering angle, are sensed automatic. and communicated to the computer system through a CAN bus interface;
- ❖ Special air ducts direct air flow from air conditioning into the trunk for cooling the computing system: array of six Pentium M computers, a Gigabit Ethernet switch, and various devices that interface to the physical sensors and the Touareg's actuators;
- ❖ A custom-made power system with backup batteries and a switch box that enables power-cycling individual system components through software (total power is 500W);
- ❖ It holds the custom interface to the Volkswagen Touareg's actuators: the brake, throttle, gear shifter and steering controller;
- ❖ Note: **a human driver could safely operate the robot as a conventional passenger car.**

“Treat autonomous navigation as a software problem”

(a)

(b)

Stanley (Stanford U.)

Stanley (Stanford U.)

(a)

(b)

(a) A laser sensor is angled downward to scan the terrain in front of the vehicle as it moves; (b) Each laser acquires a three-dimensional 3D point cloud over time. The 3-d point cloud is analyzed for drivable terrain/potential obstacles.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(a) a raw image; (b) the processed image with the laser quadrilateral and a pixel classification; (c) the pixel classification before thresholding; and (d) horizon detection for sky removal.

(a)

(b)

(a) Search regions for the road detection module: The occurrence of obstacles is determined along a sequence of lines parallel to the RDDF; and (b) the result of the road estimator is shown in blue, behind the vehicle. The road is bounded by two small berms.

Stanley (Stanford U.)

(a) The reading of the center beam of one of the lasers, integrated over time some of the terrain is scanned twice.; (b) shows 3D point cloud; (c) resulting map without probabilistic analysis, and d map with probabilistic analysis. The map possesses a phantom obstacle, large enough to force the vehicle off the road.

Path planning in a 2D search space: (a) Paths that change lateral offsets with the min possible lateral acceleration for a fixed plan horizon; (b) the same for the max lateral acceleration.

Stanley (Stanford U.)

$$\delta(t) = \psi(t) + \arctan \frac{kx(t)}{u(t)}, \quad x(t) \approx x(0)\exp -kt$$

- ❖ The velocity recommender module sets an appropriate maximum velocity based on estimated terrain slope and roughness;
- ❖ The velocity recommender is characterized by two parameters:
 - The maximum allowable shock, and the linear recovery rate;
 - Both are learned from human driving;
- ❖ The steering controller accepts the trajectory generated by the path planner, the UKF pose and velocity estimate, and the measured steering wheel angle;
 - ❖ Based on a nonlinear feedback function of cross-track error;
- ❖ Damping the difference while time delay in control, inertia in steering column, more energy to dissipate as speed increases;

Stanley (Stanford U.)

- ❖ RADAR uses linear frequency shift keying modulated LFMSK transmit wave form;
- ❖ it is normally used for adaptive cruise control.
- ❖ RADAR proved highly effective in detecting large frontal obstacles such as abandoned vehicles in desert terrain.
- ❖ RADAR was tasked to screen the road at a range beyond the laser sensors.
- ❖ If a potential obstacle was detected, the system limits speed to 25 mph so that the lasers could detect the obstacle in time for collision avoidance.
- ❖ The probability of encountering large frontal obstacles was small in high-speed zones; and even if those existed, the vision system would very likely detect them.
- ❖ The technical risks associated with the RADAR system outweighed its benefits.

Junior (Stanford U.)

- A modified 2006 **Volkswagen Passat Wagon**, a 4-cylinder turbo diesel injection engine, equipped with 5 laser rangefinders (manufactured by IBEO, Riegl, Sick, and Velodyne), an Applanix GPS-aided inertial navigation system, five BOSCH radars, two Intel quad core, and a custom drive-by-wire interface developed by Volkswagen;
- The 140 hp vehicle is equipped with a limited-torque steering motor, an electronic brake booster, electronic throttle, gear shifter, parking brake, and turn signals;
- A custom interface board provides **computer control** over the vehicle elements;
- The engine provides **electric power** to the computing system via a high-current prototype alternator, by a battery-backed electronically controlled power system;
- The cabin is equipped with **switches** that enable a human driver to engage various electronic interface components at will.

Junior (Stanford U.)

- Each module communicates with other modules via an anonymous publish/subscribe message passing protocol, based on the IPC Toolkit.

- **Sensor interfaces:**
 - Manage communication with the vehicle and individual sensors and make resulting sensor data available to the rest of the SW modules.
- **Perception modules:**
 - Segment the environ. data into moving vehicles and static obstacles;
 - Also provide precision localization to the digital map of the environ.
- **Navigation modules:**
 - Determine the behavior with a number of motion planners plus a hierarchical FSMs for behaviors and preventing deadlocks;
- **Drive-by-wire interface:**
 - Controls are passed and enables SW control of the throttle, brake, steering, gear shifting, turn signals, and emergency brake.
- **Global services:**
 - Provide logging, time stamping, message-passing support, and watchdog functions to keep the software running reliably.

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Process name	Computer	Description
PROCESS-CONTROL	1	starts and restarts processes, adds process control via IPC
APPLANIX	1	Applanix interface (via IPC).
LDLRS1 & LDLRS2	1	Sick LDLRS laser interface (via IPC).
IBEO	1	IBEO laser interface (via IPC).
SICK1 & SICK2	1	Sick LMS laser interfaces (via IPC).
RIEGL	1	Riegl laser interface (via IPC).
VELODYNE	1	Velodyne laser interface (via IPC and shared memory). This module also projects the 3d points using Applanix pose information.
CAN	1	CAN bus interface
RADAR1 - RADAR5	1	Radar interfaces (via IPC).
PERCEPTION	1	IPC/Shared Memory interface of Velodyne data, obstacle detection, dynamic tracking and scan differencing
RNDF_LOCALIZE	1	1D localization using RNDF
HEALTHMON	1	logs computer health information (temperature, processes, CPU and memory usage)
PROCESS-CONTROL	2	start/restarts processes and adds process control over IPC
CENTRAL	2	IPC-server
PARAM_SERVER	2	central server for all parameters
ESTOP	2	IPC/serial interface to DARPA E-stop
HEALTHMON	2	monitors the health of all modules
POWER	2	IPC/serial interface to power-server (relay card)
PASSAT	2	IPC/serial interface to vehicle interface board
CONTROLLER	2	vehicle motion controller
PLANNER	2	path planner and hybrid A* planner

Table of processes running during the Urban Challenge

Flow diagram of the Software

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- ❖ In many situations, multiple measurements have to be integrated over time even for **static environment mapping**;
- ❖ Integrating multiple measurements is also necessary to cope with certain blind spots in the near range of the vehicle;
- ❖ The exact **map update** rule relies on the standard Bayesian framework for evidence accumulation;
- ❖ This safeguards the robot against spurious obstacles that only show up in a small number of measurements;
- ❖ A key downside of accumulating static data over time into a map arises from objects that move;
 - In each polar direction away from the robot, the grid cells between the robot and the nearest detected object are observed to be free;
 - Hence, no map updating takes place beyond this range.

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- **Moving object detection** is performed on a synthetic 2-D scan of the environment, synthesized from the various laser sensors by extracting the range to the nearest detected obstacle along an evenly spaced array of synthetic range sensors;
- **Precise localization** uses road reflectivity and curb-like obstacles;
 - ❖ The filter for localization is a 1-d (1-D) histogram filter that estimates the vehicle's lateral offset relative to the RNDF;

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- The global **path planner** is activated for each new checkpoint, also as a permanent road blockage leads to a topology change of the road network;
- The **DP** algorithm recursively computes for each cell in a discrete RNDP the cumulative costs of moving from each such location to the goal point;
- The cost function implements a balance btw navigation time and risk;
- The actual vehicle **navigation** is handled differently for common road navigation and the free-style navigation necessary for parking lots;
 - ❖ For free-form navigation in parking lots, utilize a second planner to generate arbitrary trajectories irres. of a specific road structure.

Boss (CMU)

- A 2007 **Chevrolet Tahoe** modified for autonomous driving to provide computer control and also to support safe and efficient testing of algorithms;
- A commercial off-the-shelf **drive-by-wire** system was integrated with electric motors to turn the steering column, depress the brake pedal, and shift the transmission;
- The back area were replaced with electronics racks, the steering was modified to remove excess compliance, and the brakes were replaced to allow faster braking and reduce heating;
- It still maintains normal human driving controls (steering wheel and brake and gas pedals) so that a safety driver can quickly and easily take control;
- Space to a custom center console with power and network outlets, for developers to power laptops and other accessories, supporting longer and more productive testing;
- A welded tube roll cage was also installed to protect human occupants in the event of a collision or rollover during testing;
- Power buses: stock Tahoe power bus remains intact with its 12-V dc battery and harnesses, auxiliary 24-V dc power system provides power for the autonomy hardware.

Boss (CMU)

constant profile

linear profile

linear ramp profile

trapezoidal profile

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}) = [v_{\text{cmd}}(\mathbf{p}, t) + \kappa_{\text{cmd}}(\mathbf{p}, s)]^T.$$

$$\mathbf{x}_F(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}) = \int_0^{t_f} \dot{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}) dt,$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}) = \mathbf{x}_C - \mathbf{x}_F(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}),$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{p} = - \left[\frac{\delta \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p})}{\delta \mathbf{p}} \right]^{-1} \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}).$$

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{free}} = [\kappa_1 \quad \kappa_2 \quad s_f]^T.$$

- The **vehicle model** describes the mapping from control inputs to state response (changes in position, orientation, velocity, etc.);
- The applied vehicle model combines a curvature limit, a curvature rate limit, maximum acceleration and deceleration, and a model of the control input latency;
- This model is simulated using a fixed-timestep Euler integration to evaluate the constraint equation;
- The linear **velocity profile** takes the form of a constant profile, linear profile, linear ramp profile, or a trapezoidal profile;
- The response to the curvature command function by the vehicle model defines the shape of the trajectory.

Boss (CMU)

Moving obstacle detection and tracking

Boss (CMU)

Smooth and sharp trajectories

- ❖ The **static obstacle mapping** system combines data from the scanning lasers on the vehicle to generate both instantaneous and temporally filtered obstacle maps;
- ❖ The instantaneous obstacle map is used in the validation of moving obstacle hypotheses;
- ❖ The temporally filtered maps are processed to remove **moving obstacles** and are filtered to reduce the number of spurious obstacles appearing in the maps;
- ❖ Whereas several algorithms were used to generate obstacle maps, only the curb detection algorithm is presented.

Boss (CMU)

- ❖ Capable of either estimating **road geometry** or **localizing** itself relative to roads with known geometry;
- ❖ To localize relative to paved roads and estimate the shape of dirt roads, which change geometry more frequently;
- ❖ The localization process can be thought of as transforming the pose provided by a GPS-based pose estimation system into a smooth coordinate frame registered to a road network;
- ❖ The localization process accumulates lane marker points (LMP) generated by laser lane marker detection;
- ❖ To robustly drive on roads where the geometry is not known a priori, the road shape estimator measures the curvature, position, and heading of roads near the vehicle;
- ❖ The **road estimator** uses an SIR filter (# 500 particles);
- ❖ **Mission planning**: the data provided in RNDF are used to create a graph that encodes the connectivity of the environment.

Boss (CMU)

High-level behaviors architecture

- The behavioral architecture is based on the concept of identifying a set of driving contexts, each of which requires the vehicle to focus on a reduced set of environmental features;
 - lane driving, intersection handling, achieving a zone pose.
- In unstructured environment (parking lot) uses **anytime D*** backward planning over state space of position, orientation and speed, variable resolution;
- “Anytime D* backward”
 - A* uses $f(n)=g(n)+\epsilon h(n)$, $\epsilon = 1$;
 - ‘Anytime’ uses $\epsilon > 1$, which will run faster but give suboptimal solution, reduce ϵ and replan if time allows ;
 - ‘D’ is dynamic, if map changes (e.g. detect new obstacle) recompute, but only for paths affected;
 - ‘backward’ starts graph expansion from vehicle instead of goal, as observable changes are usually local.

Boss (CMU)

Components of the behavioral subsystem

Goal selection components

State estimator: combines the vehicle's position with the world model to produce a discrete and semantically rich representation of the vehicle's logical position with the RNDF.

Goal selector: uses the current logical location as reported by state estimator to generate the next series of local goals for execution by the motion planner; these will be either lane goals or zone goals.

Drive down road

Lane selector: uses the surrounding traffic conditions to determine the optimal lane to be in at any instant and executes a merge into that lane if it is feasible.

Merge planner: determines the feasibility of a merge into a lane proposed by lane selector.

Current scene reporter: the current scene reporter distills the list of known vehicles and discrete obstacles into a few discrete data elements, most notably the distance to and velocity of the nearest vehicle in front of Boss in the current lane.

Distance keeper: uses the surrounding traffic conditions to determine the necessary in-lane vehicle safety gaps and govern the vehicle's speed accordingly.

Vehicle driver: combines the outputs of distance keeper and lane selector with its own internal rules to generate a so-called "motion parameters" message, which governs details such as the vehicle's speed, acceleration, and desired tracking lane.

Handle intersection

Precedence estimator: uses the list of known other vehicles and their state information to determine precedence at an intersection.

Pan-head planner: aims the pan-head sensors to gain the most relevant information for intersection precedence decisions.

Transition manager: manages the discrete-goal interface between the behavioral executive and the motion planner, using the goals from goal selector and the gating function from precedence estimator to determine when to transmit the next sequence of goals.

Boss (CMU)

TROCS (Tartan Racing Operator Control Station) is an extensible GUI for developers to both monitor telemetry from Boss while it is driving and replay data offline for algorithm analysis.

Talos (MIT)

- The **Land Rover LR3** provided a maneuverable and robust platform for its excellent maneuverability, small turning radius, and large payload capacity;
- EMC installed computer-controlled servos on the gear shift and steering column and a single servo for throttle and brake actuation;
- A safe way of switching from normal human-driven control to autonomous control;
- Primary power: Honda 6,000-W R/V (recreational vehicle) generator;
- Electric power: 240 V Quanta blade server, up to 4,000 W;
- The 240-V ac power is fed to twin Acumentrics rugged **UPS 2500** units that provide backup power to the computer and sensor systems;
- ADU(**autonomous driving unit**): link between the computers and the vehicle, also an interface to the drive-by-wire system from EMC;
 - ❑ The ADU incorporated a watchdog timer that would cause the vehicle to automatically enter PAUSE state if the computer either generated invalid commands or stopped sending commands entirely;
 - ❑ The ADU also implemented the interface to the buttons and displays in the cabin and DARPA E-stop.

Talos (MIT)

Three of the key novel features

- (1) a **perception-based navigation** strategy,
- (2) a unified planning and control (PNC) architecture,
- (3) a powerful new software infrastructure.

Additional components:

- Electronic Mobility Controls (EMC) drive-bywire system (AEVIT)
- Honda EVD6010 internal power generator
- 2 Acumentrics uninterruptible power supplies
- Quanta blade server computer system (the unbranded equivalent of Fujitsu Primergy BX600)
- Applanix POS-LV 220 GPS/INS
- Velodyne HDL-64 LIDAR
- 12 SICK LIDARs
- 5 Point Grey Firefly MV cameras
- 15 Delphi radars

Talos (MIT)

	Talos-I	Talos-II
Type of car	Ford Escape	Land Rover LR3
Fly-by-wire conversion	AEVIT/EMC	AEVIT/EMC
IMU/GPS System	XSeus/Navcom	Applanix POS LV220
Computer system	Fujitsu-Siemens BX600 Blade Cluster	Fujitsu-Siemens BX600 Blade Cluster
Power generation	Honda EU2000i/Honda EU3000iS	Honda EV/D6010 internal RV generator
Power conditioning	APC UPS	Dual Accumetrics 2500 220V Ruggedized UPS
Lidars	SICK LMS-291 S05 lidars	SICK LMS 291-S05 lidars
Cameras	Pt. Grey Firefly MV	Pt. Grey Firefly MV
Radars	Delphi ACC3	Delphi ACC3

Talos (MIT)

Vehicle operating modes

- ADU
- EMC drive-by-wire
- External kill switches
- Dash mounted switch panel
- Remote E-stop
- Vehicle mode annunciators
- Light tower and lightbar

Talos (MIT)

- Road paint detector.
- Lane tracker.
- Obstacle detector.
- Hazard detector.
- Fast vehicle detector.
- Positioning module.
- Navigator module.
- Drivability map.
- Motion planner (trajectory).
- Controller.

Talos (MIT)

Perception Dataflow / Architecture

Talos (MIT)

Ground model

Algorithm RRT-based planning algorithm

Talos (MIT)

- 1: repeat
- 2: Receive the current vehicle states and environment.
- 3: Propagate the states by the computation time limit.
- 4: repeat
- 5: Take a sample for the input to the controller
- 6: Select a node in the tree using heuristics
- 7: Propagate from the selected node to the sample
- 8: if The propagated path is feasible with the drivability map then
- 9: Add branch nodes on the path.
- 10: Add the sample and the branch nodes to the tree.
- 11: for Each newly added node v do
- 12: Propagate to the target
- 13: if The propagated path is feasible with the Drivability Map then
- 14: Add the path to the tree
- 15: Set the cost of the propagated path as the upper bound of cost-to-go at v
- 16: end if
- 17: end for
- 18: end if
- 19: until Time limit is reached
- 20: Choose the best trajectory in the tree, and check the feasibility with the latest Drivability Map
- 21: if The best trajectory is infeasible then
- 22: Remove the infeasible portion from the tree and Go to line 2
- 23: end if
- 24: Send the best trajectory to the controller
- 25: until Vehicle reaches the target.

The **speed controller** is a low-bandwidth controller with the following gains:

$$u = K_p(v - v_{ref}) + K_i \int (v - v_{ref})dt,$$

$$K_p = 0.2,$$

$$K_i = 0.04.$$

The low-level **steering control** uses a modified version of pursuit control law to steer vehicle along the desired path.

$$\delta = -\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{L \sin \eta}{L_1/2 + l_a \cos \eta} \right),$$

where L is the constant vehicle wheelbase, l_a is the constant distance between the pure pursuit anchor point and the rear axle, η is the angle between the vehicle heading and reference path direction, and L_1 is the look-ahead distance that determines how far ahead on the reference path the controller should be aiming.

Talos (MIT)

The **navigator** is responsible for planning the high level behavior of the vehicle, including

- shortest route to the next MDF checkpoint
- intersection precedence, crossing, and merging
- generation of the goal for the motion planner
- generation of the fail-safe timers
- blockage re-planning
- passing
- turn signaling

Talos (MIT)

Screenshot of the real-time visualization tool running “live” for an intersection testing scenario, showing RNDF and vehicle navigation information (white, green, red), lidar (blue, yellow) and camera (lower right) data, and vehicle tracker output (blue solid in intersection)

Talos (MIT)

Screenshot of SimCreator simulation environment, including MIT vehicle and traffic vehicles

Talos (MIT)

- ❑ Delphi's millimeter wave OEM automotive adaptive cruise control **radars** were used for long range vehicle tracking.
- ❑ The narrow FOV of these radars (around 18 deg) required a tiling of 15 radars to achieve the desired 240-deg **FOV**.
- ❑ The radars require a dedicated **CAN** bus interface each.
- ❑ To support 15 CAN bus networks, used eight internally developed CAN to Ethernet adaptors (EthCANs), then each adaptor could support two CAN buses.

Fifteen 18-deg radars yield a wide FOV

Talos (MIT)

- ❑ The **radar** subsystem complements the LIDAR subsystem by detecting moving objects at ranges beyond the reliable detection range of the LIDARs.
- ❑ In addition to range and bearing, the radars directly measure the closing rate of moving objects using **Doppler**, greatly simplifying data association.
- ❑ The radar subsystem maintains a set of active **tracks**, propagate these tracks forward in time whenever the radar produces new data, compare the predicted position and velocity to the data returned by the radar.
- ❑ The first step in tracking is to **associate** radar detections to any active tracks. The radar produces Doppler closing rates that are consistently within a few meters per second of the truth: if the predicted closing rate and the measured closing rate differ by more than 2 m/s, disallow a match; otherwise, the closest track (in the *XY plane*) is chosen for each measurement.

Talos (MIT)

- ❑ If the closest track is more than 6.0 m from the radar detection, a new track is created instead.
- ❑ Each **track** records all **radar** measurements that have been matched to it over the last second, then update each track's position and velocity model by computing a LS fit of a constant-velocity model to the $(x, y, time)$ data from the radars.
- ❑ *Weight* recent observations more strongly than older observations because the target may be accelerating. For simplicity, fitted the constant-velocity model using just the (x, y) points.
- ❑ The radars cannot easily distinguish between small, innocuous objects (such as a bolt lying on the ground, or a sewer grate) and large objects (such as cars).
- ❑ To avoid false positives, used the radars only to detect moving objects.

Talos (MIT)

(a)

(b)

Radar tracking three vehicles. (a) Front right camera showing three traffic vehicles, one oncoming. (b) Points: Raw radar detections with tails representing the **Doppler velocity**. Rectangles: Resultant vehicle tracks with speed in meters per second (size is simply for visualization).

Odin (Virginia Tech.)

- Team VictorTango divided the problem posed by the Urban Challenge into three major parts: **base vehicle platform, perception, and planning**;
- A modified 2005 **Hybrid Ford Escape** named Odin (The use of the hybrid-electric Ford Escape provides numerous advantages in the areas of on-board power generation, reliability, safety and autonomous operation);
 - ❑ Since the stock steering, shifting and throttle systems on the Hybrid Escape are already drive-by-wire, these systems can be controlled electronically by emulating the command signals, eliminating the complexity and failure potential associated with the addition of external actuators.
 - ❑ The stock hybrid power system is able to provide sufficient power for sensors and computers without the need for a separate generator.
- **Perception**: the Localization component determines the vehicle position and orientation in the world, the Object Classification component detects obstacles and classifies them as either static or dynamic;
- The **planning** uses a Hybrid Deliberative-Reactive model dividing upper level decisions and lower level reactions into separate components;
 - ❑ These components run concurrently at independent rates, allowing the vehicle to react to emergency situations without needing to re-plan an entire route;
 - ❑ The Route Planner component is responsible for determining which road segments and zones the vehicle should use to travel to all checkpoints.

Odin (Virginia Tech.)

- Sensors:
- 2 IBEO Alasca XT
 - 2 Cameras
 - 4 SICK LMS
 - 1 IBEO Alasca A0

Route Network Definition File (RNDF)
Cubic Spline Interpolations

Odin (Virginia Tech.)

System Architecture

Object Classification

Odin (Virginia Tech.)

Driving Behaviors

Motion Planning

Odin (Virginia Tech.)

Screenshot of simulated Odin encountering a roadblock

Cornell in DARPA Urban Challenge

Sensor Configuration

- SICK 1D LIDAR (60m)
- Ibeo 4x160 LIDAR (150m)
- Velodyne 64x360 LIDAR
- DELPHI mm-wave RADAR
- MobilEye SeeQ Vision
- Front and rear cameras
- Litton LN-200 IMU
- Septentrio 3-antenna GPS
- Trimble/Omnistar GPS
- Stock CAN wheel encoders

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2007 Chevrolet Tahoe

Pose Estimation

- ❑ Integrate information from multiple sources
 - ❖ Septentrio GPS, Trimble GPS, IMU, wheels, RNDF, visual detection of lanes and stop lines
 - ❖ Reject big jumps ❑
- ❑ Particle filter to estimate lane probabilities
 - ❖ 2000 particles @ 100Hz ❑
- ❑ Accurate in GPS blackout
 - ❖ E.g., m-level during 8 min. outage

Steering

Brake

Trans.

Alternator

Invert./batt.

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Processing Overview

- Segment LIDAR data
- Determine number of objects
- Update/initialize
- Estimate tracked object metadata
- Maintain stable track IDs

Using LIDAR, RADAR (and vision)

- Vision had too many false positives/negatives

Segmenting LIDAR Data

- Cluster Ibeo data using Euclidean distance

Note: Center of mass or fixed point not reliable

Ground hits Stable clusters Unstable clusters

Ego-vehicle

3 Ibeos, 12 colored
laser beams

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Ground Estimation

- ❑ Long-range, LIDAR such as Ibeo, SICK generates false alarms
- ❑ Grid-based ground model from dense LIDAR
 - ❖ Lower envelope of hits in nearby region from all LIDARs
 - ❖ Use to classify hits as ground, low, high

Object Tracking

- ❑ Object state: object-centered coord frame + observed points
 - 2D rigid body transform (relative)
 - Ground speed (absolute), heading (relative)
- ❑ EKF predicts point locations forward
- ❑ Update coordinate frame and velocity
- ❑ Replace points with new observed data
- ❑ Particle filter for alternative obj hypotheses (data association)
 - Small number of particles – 4 in DUC

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Sensor Integration/Fusion

- LIDAR, RADAR (/vision) combined at object tracking level
 - Data consistent with existing track or start new
- New tracks must meet certain requirements
 - E.g., for LIDAR need to see both occluding contours
- Often 50+ simultaneous tracks in DUC

Tracking vs. Occupancy

- Object identity over time enables perceiving others' behaviors
- Currently at level required for intersection precedence and following but not more complex behaviors
 - ✓ Problems with long time periods and with changes in shape of object wrt vehicle as move
- Opportunity/need for better perception of behaviors

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Decision Making and Execution

- ❑ Behavioral (macro planning)
 - E.g., route (re)planning – like consumer nav tools ❑
- ❑ Tactical (local planning)
 - E.g., when to change lanes, pass ❑
- ❑ Operational (plan execution)
 - E.g., path generation, obstacle avoidance

Object Meta Data

- ❑ Attributes for higher-level planning
 - Car-like or not, HMM on width
 - Stopped or not, HMM on speed
 - Occluded or not, geometric reasoning
 - Lane probab., Monte Carlo sampling of object locations
 - ❖ From vehicle relative to map relative
 - ❖ Less certain with distance

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Track ID's

- ❑ Maintain consistent identifiers for objects across frames
 - ❖ Global maximum likelihood matching to previous frame
 - ❖ Stable measures used to match tracks and new objects
 - Closest point and occlusion bearings
 - ❖ DP over likelihood table to solve for correspondences

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Operational: Path Planner

- ❑ ❑ Constrained nonlinear optimization
 - Base path, lane boundary constraints, target paths, starting/ending heading/position ❑
- ❑ Label obstacles as being to left or right ❑
- ❑ Complex but natural behavior by modifying constraints ❑
- ❑ Off the shelf nonlinear solver – LOQO ❑ 10Hz rate

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Tactical Planner

- ❑ Separate tactical components for road, intersection, zone, blockage
 - Designed to recover from not properly achieving desired state or starting in unknown state
- ❑ Road tactical
 - Monitors for forward, rear, lateral regions
 - E.g., closest vehicle in forward direction
 - States such as StayInLane, ChangeLanes

ESTRO: AV at ETRI (Korea)

ESTRO: AV at ETRI (Korea)

On-road markers extraction: (a) original image of normal road, (b) extraction for speed bumper, (c) original image of stop line, (d) extraction for stop line, (e) original image of lane, (f) extraction for lane.

Curb extraction: (a) image of continuous curb, (b) extraction for continuous curb, (c) image of discontinuous curbs, and (d) extraction for discontinuous curbs.

LiDAR (Light Detection And Ranging)

- LIDAR utilizes a beam of light typically with an infrared laser diode that is reflected off of a rotating mirror.
 - As the light hits non-absorbing objects the light is reflected back to a sensor that creates a map similar to the radar block diagram.
- Higher-end LIDAR systems utilize multiple beams to provide multiple distance measurements simultaneously.
 - Utilized in higher fidelity applications where approximating 3 dimensions are required .
- Higher costs and require additional packaging space that prohibit their use.
 - Spinning LIDAR system used in Google's autonomous vehicle costs approximately \$70,000.
 - Low speed LIDAR systems, like Continental AG, which utilizes typically 4 beams of light
 - The system used by Google for full autonomy, from Velodyne Inc., utilizes 32-64 beams for higher fidelity measurements.
- LIDAR not as accurate as RADAR systems for detecting speed.
 - Inability to utilize the Doppler Effect compared to RADAR.
 - Google vehicle utilizes both LIDAR and RADAR sensors.

LiDAR

- A pulse of light is emitted and the precise time is recorded
- The reflection of that pulse is detected and the precise time is recorded
- Using the constant speed of light, LiDAR instrument can calculate the distance between itself and the target with high accuracy
- Knowing the position and orientation of the sensor, the XYZ coordinate of the reflective surface can be calculated
- By repeating this in quick succession the instrument builds up a complex and accurate map of the car's surroundings

History of LiDAR

- Laser ranging developed in the 1960s
- LiDAR terrain mapping began in 1970s
- Initial systems were “single beam”, profiling devices
- Early use for terrain mapping limited by lack of accurate geo-referencing
- Early systems used for bathymetry
- Development of global positioning systems and inertial navigation (measurement) systems improved accuracy

Auto Calibration of Lidar & Camera

Internal parameters (or intrinsic) govern the internal workings of the 3D sensor:

- ❖ ToF cameras require calibration of camera projection matrix, and phase-delay latency.
- ❖ Velodyne Lidar requires recovering a scale, offset and the elevation angle for each of the rotating laser scanners.
- ❖ A line scanning Lidar mounted on rotating platform estimating a rigid body transform btw the instantaneous center of rotation of the Lidar's spinning mirror (LICR) and that of the platform motor (MICR).

```

Input:  $S_1 = \{ {}^M X(j) : \phi_j < \pi \}_j^N$ 
        $S_2 = \{ {}^M Y(m) : \phi_m \geq \pi \}_m^M$ 
 $r$  maximum radius to search for neighbors
Output:  ${}^M H_{\mathcal{L}}$  internal calibration transform
// Initialize
 ${}^M H_{\mathcal{L}} \leftarrow I_{4 \times 4}$ ;
for  $i \leftarrow I$  do
    // Compute neighbors and normals
    for  $j \leftarrow |X|$  do
         $\{y\}_k^K \leftarrow \text{RadiusSearch}(X_j; S_2, r)$ ;
         $Y_l^k \leftarrow \text{ClosestPoint}(X_j; \{y\})$ ;
         $\eta_k \leftarrow \text{EstimateNormal}(\{y\})$ ;
    end
    while not converged do
         ${}^M H_{\mathcal{L}} = \underset{H}{\text{argmin}} \left\{ \sum_j \sum_k \|\eta_k \cdot (X_j - H Y_l^k)\|^2 \right\}$ 
    end
end
end
    
```

Algorithm 1: Spinning lidar internal calibration.

Calibration of a rotating multi-beam Lidar

- Velodyne HDL-64E S2: it consists of 64 lasers located on a spinning head which can spin at a rate of 5 to 15 Hz, and provides 3D data about its surroundings at a rate of 1.33 million points per second.
- Ibeo LUX: it scans its surroundings in four parallel layers.
- A multi-beam lidar system is modelled as a set of rays, i.e. straight lines, which define the position and orientation of laser beams in a sensor-fixed coordinate frame.
- The intrinsic calibration for such systems is the estimation of parameters that define the position and orientation of each of the laser beams.
- A calibration environment can be designed and constructed to acquire lidar data for calibration.

Calibration of a rotating multi-beam Lidar

Each of the 64 lasers is characterized by 5 parameters that are required to convert the distance value returned by the laser to 3D point coordinates.

$$D = D_{ret} + D_{corr}$$

$$D_{xy} = D * \cos(\theta) - V_o * \sin(\theta)$$

$$P_x = D_{xy} * \sin(\beta) - H_o * \cos(\beta)$$

$$P_y = D_{xy} * \cos(\beta) + H_o * \sin(\beta)$$

$$P_z = D * \sin(\theta) + V_o * \cos(\theta)$$

Unsupervised Calibration for Multi-beam Lasers

- ❖ Recover optimal parameters for each beam's orientation and distance-response function, also a fully probabilistic generative model for each beam's remittance response to surfaces of varying reflectivity;
- ❖ Recover the sensor's extrinsic pose relative to the robot's coordinate frame;
- ❖ Requires no specific calibration target, only assuming **contiguous surfaces**;
- ❖ An energy function on point clouds which penalizes points that are far away from surfaces defined by points from other beams as:

$$J = \sum_{b_i=1}^B \sum_{b_j=b_i-N}^{b_i+N} \sum_k w_k \|\eta_k \cdot (p_k - m_k)\|^2$$

point-to-plane ICP

→ the surface normal

- ❖ **Grid search** for extrinsic calibration only, but take empirical derivatives of the energy function across pairs of beams for intrinsic calibration;
- ❖ A generative model of each beam's response to surfaces using EM.

Unsupervised Calibration for Multi-beam Lasers

(a) Horribly uncalibrated sensor.

(b) After 40 iterations of optimization

(c) After 80 iterations of optimization

(d) After 300 iterations of optimization

Extrinsic Calibration of LiDAR-Camera

Target-based:

Zhang'04: 2D laser scanner and camera, the checkerboard pattern;
Mei & Rives'06: 2D laser range finder and an omnidirectional camera;
Unnikrishnan & Hebert'05, Pandey'10: extension to 3d laser scanner and camera;
Nunnez'09: IMU;
Mirzaei'12: geometric constraint between the laser points and the plane normal;
Zhou & Deng'12: decouples the estimation of rotation from translation;
Li'13: stereo vision and 2D lidar;
Li'07: a triangular checkerboard target;
Rodriguez'08: circle-based multi-layer lidar-camera;
Gong'13: a trihedral object for 3d lidar and camera;
Alempijevic'06: MI-based calibration;

Targetless:

Boughorbal'00, Williams'04: χ^2 test;
Scaramuzza'07: 3D laser scanner and omni-directional camera;
Levinson & Thrun'10: surfaces;
Jian & Vemuri'11: entropy with GMM;
Levinson & Thrun'12: correlation of depth discontinuities and edge;
Wang'12, Taylor'12, Pandey'12: MI;
Sheehan'12: quality perf. by crispness;
Napier'13: 2D lidar and camera, IMU;
Moghadam'13: 3D line features.

Note: Devices for 3-d laser point clouds

Push broom;
Nodder / rocker;
Rotational.

Targetless Lidar-Camera Calibration

- ❖ Plain depth info. is expected from the lidar scan;
- ❖ What can be done when neither a special target nor point correspondences are available?
- ❖ Regarded as a 2D-3D registration problem using a minimum of one (for extrinsic) or two (for intrinsic-extrinsic) planar regions visible in both cameras;
- ❖ The registration is accomplished by solving system of nonlinear equations based on that the alignment of nonlinear shape deformations are recovered via the solution of a special system of equations.

Targetless Lidar-Camera Calibration

Input: 3D point cloud and 2D binary image representing the same region, and the calibration matrix K

Output: Parameters of the camera matrix P

1. Normalize the input 3D points into the unit cube and 2D points into unit square centered in the origin;
2. Triangulate the region represented by the 3D point cloud;
3. Construct the nonlinear equations;
4. Initialize camera matrix as $P=[I|o]$;
5. Solve the nonlinear system of equation with the L-M algorithm;
6. Unnormalize the solution.

Targetless Lidar-Camera Calibration

On-line Calibration of Multi LIDARs on Mobile

1. The original non-linear calibration model is reformulated as a second-order cone program (SOCP), solved by interior point methods (IPM).
2. A priori information such as a default LIDAR calibration, calibration tolerances, etc., can be readily modeled.
 - 1) Operate LIDARs while driving through a calibration loop.
 - 2) Automatically segment robust LIDAR features from each calibration loop.
 - 3) Recover inter-loop feature correspondences across successive calibration loops.
 - 4) Estimate LIDAR calibration using the recovered point correspondences through 2nd-order cone programming.

On-line Calibration of Multi LIDARs on Mobile

Given the vehicle pose (R_V^W, T_V^W) , get LiDAR extrinsic calibration parameters $(R_{\mathcal{L}}^V, T_{\mathcal{L}}^V)$

SOCP

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\Delta R_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V, T_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V, \hat{X}_{j,W}} \quad & t \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i=1}^{N_l} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \|\hat{X}_{j,W} - X_{j,W}^*\|^2 \leq t \\ & \|\Delta \Phi_{x_i}\| \leq \delta_{x_i}, \quad i = 1 : N_l \\ & \|\Delta \Phi_{y_i}\| \leq \delta_{y_i}, \quad i = 1 : N_l \\ & \|\Delta \Phi_{z_i}\| \leq \delta_{z_i}, \quad i = 1 : N_l \\ & \|T_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V - \hat{T}_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V\| \leq \epsilon_i, \quad i = 1 : N_l \\ & \|X_{j,W}^* - X_{i,W}^* - T_{t_i}^{t_j}\| \leq \beta_{ij}, \\ & \quad i = 1 : 2 : N_t, \quad j = 2 : 2 : N_t \end{aligned}$$

$$X_{j,\mathcal{L}_i} = [x_{j,\mathcal{L}_i}, y_{j,\mathcal{L}_i}, z_{j,\mathcal{L}_i}]^T \quad X_W = R_V^W \cdot (R_{\mathcal{L}}^V \cdot X_{\mathcal{L}} + T_{\mathcal{L}}^V) + T_V^W$$

$$\hat{X}_{j,W} = R_V^W(t)(\hat{R}_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V(I + \Delta R_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V)X_{j,\mathcal{L}_i} + T_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V) + T_V^W(t)$$

$$R_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V \approx \hat{R}_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V(I + \Delta R_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V)$$

$$\Delta R_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \Delta \Phi_z & -\Delta \Phi_y \\ -\Delta \Phi_z & 0 & \Delta \Phi_x \\ \Delta \Phi_y & -\Delta \Phi_x & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_{\mathcal{L}_i}^V = U_i D_i V_i^T \longrightarrow R_{\mathcal{L}_i}^{*V} = U_i I V_i^T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_l} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \sum_{k=1}^{N_c} W_{i,j,k} \|\hat{X}_{i,j,k,W} - X_{j,W}^* - S_k\|^2 \leq t$$

GPS bias $S_k = [s_{x_k}, s_{y_k}, s_{z_k}]^T, \quad k = 1 \dots N_c$

$$S_1 \equiv [0, 0, 0]^T$$

Autocalibration of LIDAR-Cameras via Edge Alignment

Algorithm 1 Joint calibration and sensor fusion

- 1: **input:** initial guess θ^0 , depth samples ψ , and intensity image x
- 2: **set:** $t \leftarrow 1$
- 3: **repeat**
- 4: $T_t \leftarrow \text{temperature}\{T_{t-1}\}$
- 5: Pick a random neighbour: $\theta^t \leftarrow \text{neighbour}\{\theta^{t-1}\}$
- 6: Update high-resolution depth ϕ_{θ^t} by solving (8).
- 7: **if** $P(\mathcal{F}(\theta^t) > \mathcal{F}(\theta^{t-1}), T) > \text{rand}(0, 1)$
- 8: **or** $\mathcal{F}(\theta^t) < \mathcal{F}(\theta^{t-1})$
- 9: $\hat{\theta} \leftarrow \theta^t$ and $\hat{\phi} \leftarrow \phi_{\theta^t}$
- 10: **until:** stopping criterion
- 11: **return:** $\hat{\theta}$ and $\hat{\phi}$

$$\mathcal{P}_{\theta}(\psi) = \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{t} \\ \mathbf{0} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \psi^T \\ \mathbf{1}^T \end{bmatrix} \right)^T,$$

$$\hat{\phi}_{\theta} = \arg \min_{\phi \in \Phi} \{ \mathcal{D}(\phi) + \lambda \mathcal{R}(\phi) \}, \quad (8) \quad \text{FISTA}$$

$$\mathcal{D}(\phi) = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathcal{P}_{\theta}\{\psi\} - \mathbf{H}\phi\|_{\ell_2}^2 \quad \mathcal{R}(\phi) = \sum_{n=1}^N w_n \|\nabla\phi\|_{\ell_2},$$

Extrinsic Calibration of Multi-layer Lidar and Camera

Algorithm 1 Circle-based Extrinsic Calibration Technique

- 1: **for** $i = 1$ to at least 6 **do**
 - 2: Estimate the i_{th} lidar calibration pose, $[{}^lN \ {}^l\hat{C}]_i$.
 - 3: Estimate the i_{th} camera calibration pose, $[{}^cN \ {}^c\hat{C}]_i$.
 - 4: **end for**
 - 5: Compute a first guess, $[\Phi_0, \Delta_0]$, for the lidar-camera rigid transformation using the linear solution
 - 6: Match the 3D circle poses estimations
 - 7: **repeat**
 - 8: Non-linear minimization using LM-algorithm
 - 9: Robust noise variance estimation σ^2 based in non-linear minimization residuals
 - 10: Weighting matrix \mathbf{W} update from M-estimator
 - 11: **until** convergence of $[\Phi, \Delta]$
 - 12: Estimate the confidence intervals
-

Hand-Eye Calibration

- **Hand-Eye Calibration** is the simultaneous computation of two unknown spatial relationships in a circle of spatial relationships, where a camera ("eye") was mounted on the gripper ("hand") of a robot;
- Transform from camera to gripper X (**hand-eye transform**)= $[R, t]$, camera motion $A=[R_a, t_a]$ and robot motion $B=[R_b, t_b]$, then the **calibration problem**: get X from $AX=XB$;

Method 1: First Determine R Then T

- **Kabsch** algorithm: $R_{a,i}R = RR_{b,i}$
- R estimated first: SVD-based
 - $P_i = X_{b,i}P_{i-1}$, $Q_i = X_{a,i}Q_{i-1}$, with $P_0 = X_{b,0}$, $Q_0 = X_{a,0}$;
 - Cross covariance matrix: $C = P^T Q$;
 - SVD: $C = VSW^T$;
 - Rotation matrix: $d = \text{sign}(\det(WV^T))$ for right handed

$$U = W \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d \end{pmatrix} V^T$$

- Then solve t: $t = (R_a - I_3)^{-1}(Rt_b - t_a)$;

Method 2: Simultaneously Determine R&T

- **Dual Quaternion:** treat rotation and translation in a unified way;

- Transform $[R, t]$ defined as $q + iq'$, with $q' = \vec{t}q/2, i^2 = 1$ (Note: q for R);
- Translation t is recovered by: $t = 2q'q$ (Note: \bar{q} is conjugate quaternion, $q\bar{q} = 1$);

- Denote camera motion \mathbf{a} , robot motion \mathbf{b} , and hand-eye transform \mathbf{q} , then **hand-eye calibration** is to solve the equation: $a = qb\bar{q}$;

- Rewrite dual quaternion as

$$q = (\cos(\theta/2), \sin(\theta/2)\vec{l}) \quad q = \begin{pmatrix} \cos((\theta + id)/2) \\ \sin((\theta + id)/2)(\vec{l} + i\vec{m}) \end{pmatrix}$$

dual angle

$$q' = (-\sin(\theta/2)d/2, \sin(\theta/2)\vec{m} + \cos(\theta/2)(d/2)\vec{l})$$

dual vector

- Equivalent to a 3-d line-based motion estimation problem as: $(0, \vec{a}) = q(0, \vec{b})\bar{q}$;

- SVD-based solution: $n > 1 \quad T = U\Sigma V^T$

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} S_1^T & S_2^T & \dots & S_n^T \end{pmatrix}^T \begin{pmatrix} \vec{a} - \vec{b} & [\vec{a} + \vec{b}]_{\times} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \vec{a}' - \vec{b}' & [\vec{a}' + \vec{b}']_{\times} & \vec{a} - \vec{b} & [\vec{a} + \vec{b}]_{\times} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} q \\ q' \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

- The last two columns in V span the null space: $\vec{v}_7^T = (\vec{u}_1^T, \vec{v}_1^T) \quad \vec{v}_8^T = (\vec{u}_2^T, \vec{v}_2^T)$

$$\begin{pmatrix} q \\ q' \end{pmatrix} = \lambda_1 \begin{pmatrix} \vec{u}_1 \\ \vec{v}_1 \end{pmatrix} + \lambda_2 \begin{pmatrix} \vec{u}_2 \\ \vec{v}_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \lambda_1^2 \vec{u}_1^T \vec{v}_1 + \lambda_1 \lambda_2 (\vec{u}_1^T \vec{v}_2 + \vec{u}_2^T \vec{v}_1) + \lambda_2^2 \vec{u}_2^T \vec{v}_2 = 0$$

- Choose the λ_1, λ_2 for the largest value for $s^2 \vec{u}_1^T \vec{u}_1 + 2s \vec{u}_1^T \vec{u}_2 + \vec{u}_2^T \vec{u}_2$ (Note: $s = \lambda_1/\lambda_2$).

Fixing the Scaling Factor in SfM

- Scaling factor in translation is unknown in SfM;
- Kabsch: Estimate rotation first;
 - Assume the scaling factor for translation $t_{a,o}$ as λ : $t_{ai} = \lambda u_{ai}$;
 - Define LS solution: $(R_{ai} - I_3)t + \lambda u_{ai} = R t_{bi}$;
 - ✦ If $R_{ai} \approx I$, then $\lambda u_{ai} \approx R t_{bi}$ (if normalized of both sides, $u_{ai} \approx R t_{bi}$);
- Dual quaternion: estimate R and t simultaneously
 - Integrate scale into dual quaternion for similarity transform;

$$q_s = q_{s_nd} + i q_{s_d} = \lambda q + i \vec{t} q / 2$$

- Scale is modeled as the norm: $\lambda = |q_s|$

- Additional constraints: $q_{s_nd} \bar{q}_{s_nd} + q_{s_d} \bar{q}_{s_d} = 0$

- Eventually it is formulated as a NLS problem:

$$f(q_{s_d}, q_{s_nd}) = \sum_i \|q_{bi_nd} q_{s_nd} - q_{s_nd} q_{ai_nd}\|^2 + \sum_i \|q_{bi_nd} q_{s_d} + s_{-1} q_{bi_d} q_{s_nd} - q_{s_nd} q_{ai_d} + q_{s_d} q_{ai_nd}\|^2 + \lambda (q_{s_nd} q_{s_d}^* + q_{s_d} q_{s_nd}^*)^2.$$

$s_{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{q_{s_nd} q_{s_d}^* + q_{s_d} q_{s_nd}^*}}$

Fixing the Scaling Factor in SfM

- Assume either unique scaling factor (PNP-based pose estimation after first stereo matching) or scaling factors (pose estimation from R&t decomposition of Essential matrix) for every camera poses;

- 1. Multiple scaling factors: $(R_{ci} - I_3)t^T + s_i t_{ci}^T = R t_{vi}^T \quad i=0,1,\dots,k$

- LS solution (k=1): $D_{(k+3) \times (k+3)} e_{k+3} = f$

$$e = \begin{bmatrix} t^T \\ s_0 \\ s_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$f = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i \leq k} (R_{ci}^T - I) R t_{vi}^T \\ t_{c0} R t_{v0}^T \\ t_{c1} R t_{v1}^T \end{bmatrix}$$

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i \leq k} (2I - R_{ci}^T - R_{ci}) & (R_{c0}^T - I) t_{c0}^T & (R_{c1}^T - I) t_{c1}^T \\ (R_{c0}^T - I) t_{c0}^T & t_{c0} t_{c0}^T & 0 \\ (R_{c1}^T - I) t_{c1}^T & 0 & t_{c1} t_{c1}^T \end{bmatrix}$$

- 2. Unique scaling factor : $(R_{ci} - I_3)t^T + s t_{ci}^T = R t_{vi}^T \quad i=0,1,\dots,k$

- LS solution (k=1): $A_{4 \times 4} b_{4 \times 1} = c_{4 \times 1}$

$$b = \begin{bmatrix} t^T \\ s \end{bmatrix}$$

$$c = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i \leq k} (R_{ci}^T - I) R t_{vi}^T \\ \sum_{i \leq k} t_{ci} R t_{vi}^T \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i \leq k} (2I - R_{ci}^T - R_{ci}) & \sum_{i \leq k} (R_{ci}^T - I) t_{ci}^T \\ \sum_{i \leq k} (R_{ci} - I) t_{ci} & \sum_{i \leq k} t_{ci} t_{ci}^T \end{bmatrix}$$

Auto extrinsic calibration by maximization mutual information

- ❑ Calculate the correlation coefficient for the reflectivity and intensity values for lidar scan-image pair at different values of the calibration parameter and observe a distinct maxima at the true value;
- ❑ Joint histogram of the laser reflectivity and the camera intensity values is least dispersed when calculated under the correct transformation parameters;
- ❑ Mutual Information (MI) based data fusion criterion to estimate the extrinsic calibration parameters between the two sensors assuming that the data is, for the most part, not corrupted by lighting artifacts;
- ❑ Marginal and joint probabilities $p(X, Y)$ are estimated by KDE, then MI is formulated as a function of extrinsic parameters;
- ❑ Apply Barzilai-Borwein (BB) steepest gradient ascent algorithm;
- ❑ Cramer Rao Lower Bound (CRLB) of variance is calculated by Fisher info.;
- ❑ It can be used for any standard laser-camera system (monocular too).

Auto extrinsic calibration by maximization mutual information

$$MI(X, Y) = H(X) + H(Y) - H(X, Y),$$

$$H(X) = - \sum_{x \in X} p_X(x) \log p_X(x),$$

$$H(Y) = - \sum_{y \in Y} p_Y(y) \log p_Y(y),$$

$$H(X, Y) = - \sum_{x \in X} \sum_{y \in Y} p_{XY}(x, y) \log p_{XY}(x, y).$$

$$\hat{p}(X = k_x, Y = k_y) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n K_{\Omega} \left(\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} X_i \\ Y_i \end{bmatrix} \right); \quad (k_x, k_y) \in ([0, 255] \times [0, 255]),$$

$$\hat{p}(X = k) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n K_{\omega}(X - X_i); \quad k \in [0, 255],$$

$$\hat{\Theta} = \arg \max_{\Theta} MI(X, Y; \Theta), \quad \Theta = [x, y, z, \phi, \theta, \psi]^T$$

$$\mathbf{G} \equiv \nabla MI(X, Y; \Theta),$$

Barzilai-Borwein (BB) steepest gradient ascent

$$\Theta_{k+1} = \Theta_k + \gamma_k \frac{\mathbf{G}_k}{\|\mathbf{G}_k\|}, \quad \gamma_k = \frac{\mathbf{s}_k^\top \mathbf{s}_k}{\mathbf{s}_k^\top \mathbf{g}_k},$$

$$\mathbf{s}_k = \Theta_k - \Theta_{k-1} \text{ and } \mathbf{g}_k = \mathbf{G}_k - \mathbf{G}_{k-1}.$$

Auto extrinsic calibration by maximization mutual information

Algorithm 1 Automatic extrinsic calibration by maximization of mutual information

- 1: **Input:** 3D Point cloud $\{\mathbf{P}_i; i = 1, \dots, n\}$, Reflectivity $\{X_i; i = 1, \dots, n\}$, Image $\{I\}$, and Initial guess $\{\Theta_0\}$
 - 2: **Output:** Estimated parameter $\{\hat{\Theta}\}$
 - 3: **while** $\|\Theta_{k+1} - \Theta_k\| > THRESHOLD$ **do**
 - 4: $\Theta_k \rightarrow [R | t]$
 - 5: Initialize the joint histogram: $Hist(X, Y) = 0$
 - 6: **for** $i = 1 \rightarrow n$ **do**
 - 7: $\tilde{\mathbf{p}}_i = K[R | t] \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_i$
 - 8: $Y_i = I(\mathbf{p}_i)$
 - 9: Update the joint histogram: $Hist(X_i, Y_i) = Hist(X_i, Y_i) + 1$
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Calculate the kernel density estimate of the joint distribution: $p(X, Y; \Theta_k)$
 - 12: Calculate the mutual information: $MI(X, Y; \Theta_k)$
 - 13: Update the current estimate: $\Theta_{k+1} = \Theta_k + \lambda F(MI(X, Y; \Theta_k))$, where F is either the gradient function or some heuristic and λ is a tuning parameter
 - 14: **end while**
-

Auto extrinsic calibration by maximization mutual information

Automatic Calibration of Multi-Modal Systems using a Gradient Orientation Measure (GOM)

Automatic Calibration of Multi-Modal Systems using a Gradient Orientation Measure (GOM)

To convert the lidar data from a list of 3-D points to a 2-D image that can be compared to the camera's images, the points are first passed into a transformation matrix that aligns the camera's and the world axis. One works as pinhole, and another (panorama) projects points onto a cylinder.

$$x_{cam} = x_0 - \frac{cx}{z} + \Delta x_{cam}, \quad y_{cam} = y_0 - \frac{cy}{z} + \Delta y_{cam}$$

$$x_{cam} = x_0 - c \arctan\left(\frac{-y}{x}\right) + \Delta x_{cam}, \quad y_{cam} = y_0 - \frac{cz}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}} + \Delta y_{cam}$$

where

x_{cam} , y_{cam} are the X and Y position of the point in the image.

x , y , z are the coordinates of points in the environment.

c is the principle distance of the model.

x_0 , y_0 are the location of the principle point in the image.

Δx , Δy are the correction terms used to account for several imperfections in the camera.

Automatic Calibration of Multi-Modal Systems using a Gradient Orientation Measure (GOM)

Let

p_x, p_y, p_v be the current points x-position, y-position and intensity-value, respectively

n_x, n_y, n_v be the neighbouring points x-position, y-position and intensity-value, respectively

$g_x, g_y, g_{mag}, g_{or}$ be the gradient in the x-direction, gradient in the y-direction, gradient-magnitude and orientation, respectively

$g_x = 0;$

$g_y = 0;$

$g_{mag} = 0;$

for neighbouring point n **do**

$x = p_x - n_x;$

$y = p_y - n_y;$

$v = p_v - n_v;$

$g_x = g_x + \frac{vx}{8};$

$g_y = g_y + \frac{vy}{8};$

$g_{mag} = g_{mag} + |\frac{v}{8}|;$

end

$g_{or} = \arctan2(g_y, g_x)$

Algorithm 1: lidar gradient calculation

To calculate gradients of 3-d points, they are first projected onto a sphere centered at the estimated location of camera.

$$x_{sphere} = \arccos\left(\frac{z}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}}\right)$$

$$y_{sphere} = \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right)$$

Automatic Calibration of Multi-Modal Systems using a Gradient Orientation Measure (GOM)

- ❑ Large changes in image intensity usually occurs due to material differences or object geometric properties;
- ❑ Therefore a reasonable assumption with multi-modal images is that these environment properties will provoke changes in both modalities;
- ❑ GOM operates by calculating how well the orientation of the gradients between two images are aligned;

$$GOM = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n |g_{(1,j)} \cdot g_{(2,j)}|}{\sum_{j=1}^n \|g_{(1,j)}\| \|g_{(2,j)}\|}$$

Automatic Calibration of Multi-Modal Systems using a Gradient Orientation Measure (GOM)

- ❖ Cost function is typically non-convex, in particular with single-scan configuration;
- ❖ Non-convex optimization required to find maximum;
- ❖ The pipeline uses particle swarm optimization (PSO);
- ❖ PSO randomly places an initial population of particles (~500) in the search space;
- ❖ On each iteration a particle moves to a new location;
- ❖ The optimizer stops once all particles have converged.

```
Let
 $r^i(t)$  be the position of particle  $i$  at time  $t$ 
 $v^i(t)$  be the velocity of particle  $i$  at time  $t$ 
 $p_n^{i,L}$  be the local best of the  $i$ th particle for the  $n$ th dimension
 $p_n^g$  be the global best for the  $n$ th dimension
 $n \in 1, 2, \dots, N$ 
 $t$  be the time
 $\Delta t$  be the time step
 $c_1$  and  $c_2$  are the cognitive and social factor constants
 $\phi_1$  and  $\phi_2$  are two statistically independent random variables uniformly distributed between 0 and 1
 $w$  be the inertial factor

for each iteration  $l$  do
  if  $f(r^i(l+1)) > f(p^{i,L}(l))$  then
    |  $p^{i,L}(l+1) = r^i$ 
  end
  if  $f(r^i(l+1)) > f(p^g(l))$  then
    |  $p^g(l+1) = r^i$ 
  end
   $v_n^i(t + \Delta t) = wv_n^i(t) + c_1\phi_1[p_n^{i,L} - x_n^i(t)]\Delta t + c_2\phi_2[p_n^g - x_n^i(t)]\Delta t$ 
   $r_n^i(t + \Delta t) = r_n^i(t) + \Delta tv_n^i(t)$ 
end
```

Algorithm 2: Particle swarm algorithm

Auto online calibration of cameras and lasers

- ❑ Probabilistic monitoring by detecting sudden miscalibration and then correction;
- ❑ Continuous calibration optimization via adjusting transform offsets in real time and tracking gradual sensor drift as it occurs;
 - The local shape of the objective function at the current parameters can be used to determine whether the sensors are calibrated.

Accurate camera-laser calibration will cause the **green** points (depth discontinuities) to coincide with the **red** edges (inverse DT) more than an inaccurate calibration will.

Auto online calibration of cameras and lasers

- Given a calibration C , project all laser points in X_i onto the image D_i using basic geometry;
- The objective function J_C over just the last w frames, where w is our window size:

$$J_C = \sum_{f=n-w}^n \sum_{p=1}^{|X^f|} X_p^f \cdot D_{i,j}^f$$

where f iterates over all frames, p iterates over all 3D points in X^f , and (i, j) refers to the coordinates in image space onto which point p projects;

- Sums up depth discontinuities at each laser return in X times “edginess” of D for some C ;
- A solution: consider the two separate distributions of F_C across a number of training frames, one for correct calibrations and the other for incorrect calibrations, then fit a Gaussian to each of the two distributions, to compute, for any value of F_C , the probability that it was sampled from one distribution versus the other.

$$P(\text{calibrated}) = \frac{e^{-.5(x-\mu_1)^2/\sigma_1^2}}{e^{-.5(x-\mu_1)^2/\sigma_1^2} + e^{-.5(x-\mu_2)^2/\sigma_2^2}}$$

Auto online calibration of cameras and lasers

Tracking calibration errors in real time.

Initially, the transform is correct.

Synthetically perturb two translation and two rotation parameters resulting in a badly mis-calibrated sensor.

With online tracking, transform updates in real time, adjusting to the perturbations, and ends up almost perfectly calculating the synthetic shift all the way.

LiDAR-based Lane Detection

Evidence mapping of 3D lidar data onto a 2D grid.
(Darker spots to high evidence for an obstacle, white cells to drivable area; unknown cells are marked as grey.)

LiDAR-based Lane Detection

Lane marker map created on intensity data only (a) with its corresponding Radon transform (b); lane marker map created on intensity data and height data (curbs) (c) with its corresponding Radon transform (d) and a 3D plot of a region of (d) to visualize the robust line estimation of the Radon transform (e).

LiDAR-based Lane Detection

LiDAR+Camera-based Lane Detection

- Raw images acquired by a set of cameras are processed independently and asynchronously to produce lane boundary detections, assisted by real-time vehicle pose estimates and (optionally) obstacles detected from lidar data.
- Spatial/temporal data fusion combines all visual detections, along with curb boundaries (optionally) obtained from lidar data, and outputs high-confidence lane candidates.
- Lanes are estimated and tracked over time, influenced by curvature constraints and priors generated from map data if available.

LiDAR+Camera-based Free Space (Drivable-Region) Detection

LiDAR+Camera-based Free Space (Drivable-Region) Detection

(a) Original; (b) bird's-eye view after homography transform; (c) result of top-hat transform; (d) result of vertical-gradient detection by Prewitt operator; (e) result after local OTSU thresholding, after the image was divided into two parts; (f) result after PPHT; (g) result after line combining; (h) final result.

LiDAR+Camera-based Drivable-Region Detection with GeoMap

Intersection Safety using Lidar and Stereo

Intersection Safety using Lidar and Stereo

LiDAR+Camera-based Road Sign Detection

LiDAR+Camera-based Traffic Light Detection

The ray d from camera lens with local position C - C_0 to the traffic light lens as

$$d = \lambda R^{-1} K^{-1}(u, v, 1)^T$$

To obtain light locations in global coordinates, record sensor log comprising both vehicle pose & camera data; Manually select lights relevant to the trajectory from video and track them using CamShift, to adjust the bounds of an ellipse such that a hue histogram taken over its interior matches that of the original selection; Modeling the perceptual offset as a bounded plane centered and oriented as the traffic light in world space; Use 'grid' to restrict implied distance from the camera, assuming a light mapping prior wrt latitude/longitude; Belief about the offset: histogram over bounded plane (normalized grid) and update recursively by Bayes rule; Given posterior of the perceptual offset over grid cells, select the cell with the most likely location of the light; Report the most likely state at that grid cell determined by data scores.

LiDAR+Camera-based Traffic Light Detection

Traffic Light Detection

Given car pose and an accurate prior map of traffic light locations, **predict** when traffic lights should be visible;
The color segmentation **classifier** used to find appropriately-sized brightly colored red and green blobs within each predicted BB;
The structure of the light as geometric **constraints** on the low-level blobs and decide which elements are actually illuminated;
Temporal **filtering** smoothes the detector output by assuming that if there is no new classification then the light state has not changed.

LiDAR + Camera-based Pedestrian and Vehicle Detection

LiDAR + Camera-based Pedestrian and Vehicle Detection

Laser-based Obstacle Detection & Tracking

Laser-based Obstacle Detection & Tracking

LIDAR rays impacting on the road create a smooth projection shown. By finding strong **distance variations** between close points, estimate the position of the object and analyse each layer independently. **A list of layer-clusters** is extracted from the cloud of points. In the presence of an **obstacle**, clusters of different layers are at the same X and Y coordinates, but at a different Z coordinate. The layer clusters are matched to each other in order to **make groups of clusters** which are located very close between them. The group composed by three or more different layers is labeled as an obstacle and an **identification** number is assigned for obstacle tracking.

In the **obstacle tracking** stage, one counter is increased when the obstacle is detected and another one is incremented when the obstacle is not detected. Those obstacles that are lost during more than five consecutive iterations are removed from the list. Obstacles detected more than five consecutive times are considered in the **path-planning** stage. The **data association** problem is solved by using the Euclidean distance between different cluster centroids.

LiDAR-based Object Detection by Voting for Voting

- ❑ The point cloud (top left) is discretised into a 3D grid;
- ❑ For each occupied cell, points are mapped to a feature vector;
- ❑ Unoccupied cells mapped to zero feature vectors. The point cloud is converted to a feature grid;
- ❑ A 3D sliding window through the feature grid, a classifier evaluates for the evidence of an object;
- ❑ The process repeats for each rotation angle.

LiDAR-based Object Detection by Voting for Voting

- For the linear classifier, deploy a linear SVM for training. An initial set of negative examples (equal to the number of positive examples) are randomly sampled from the training data taking care not to overlap with any positive examples. Taking this initial set of training examples, adopt the standard hard negative mining technique.
- After training, the classifier is applied back on all the training frames. All false positive detections from this classifier on all the training frames are collated, and sorted in descending order of the detection score.
- The first N (or all of the false positives if there are less than N of them) are then taken and added to the set of negative examples. The classifier is then retrained with this updated training set and
- this process may iterate for a predefined number of rounds.
- Fix N to be 10000 and conduct 20 rounds of hard negative mining.

Left column: hard (but not moderate), instances containing # of measurements $m < 50$.
Middle column: moderate (but not easy), instances containing # of measurements $50 \leq m < 150$.
Right column: easy, instances containing #s of measurements $m \geq 150$.

Motion-based Detection/Tracking in 3D LiDAR Scans

- Model-free for detecting/tracking dynamic objects in 3D LiDAR scans by a sensor.
- Motion cues, not any prior information about the objects.
- Sequentially detect multiple motions and segment objects using a Bayesian approach.
- For robustly tracking objects, utilize estimated motion models.

Motion-based Detection/Tracking in 3D LiDAR Scans

The framework consists of modules for motion detection, tracking the sensor, and tracking dynamic objects.

Generative Object Detection/Tracking in 3D Range

- Generative object detection which allows the tracker to robustly extract objects of varying sizes and shapes from the observations.
- Generalize over a wide range of object classes matching assumptions.
- All parameters involved in the detection process obey a clean probabilistic interpretation.
- For tracking dynamic objects, employ a standard multi-hypothesis approach which essentially bases on the linear Kalman state estimation filter.

Algorithm 1: detectObjects($\mathbf{Z}_{1:N}$, Θ_x , Θ_o)

```
Input: Set of 3D range observations  $\mathbf{Z}_{1:N} = \{z_1, \dots, z_N\}$ 
Input: State model parameters  $\Theta_x$ 
Input: Clustering model parameters  $\Theta_o$ 
Output: Object mapping  $c : z_i \mapsto l_i$ 
Output: Updated state model parameters  $\Theta'_x$ 

// State estimation
 $\mathbf{Z}_{dyn} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
foreach  $z_i \in \mathbf{Z}_{1:N}$  do
     $\Theta'_x \leftarrow \text{updateStateModel}(\Theta_x, z_i)$ 
    Evaluate  $p(x_i = 1 \mid z_i, \Theta'_x)$  using (4) and [13]
    if  $p(x_i = 1 \mid z_i, \Theta'_x) \geq p_{dyn}$  then
         $\mathbf{Z}_{dyn} \leftarrow \mathbf{Z}_{dyn} \cup \{z_i\}$ 
    end
end
// Clustering
foreach  $z_i \in \mathbf{Z}_{dyn}$  do
     $c(z_i) \leftarrow l_i$  // Initialize labels
end
while  $\mathbf{Z}_{dyn} \neq \emptyset$  do
    foreach  $z_i \in \mathbf{Z}_{dyn}$  do
         $\mathbf{Z}_{dyn} \leftarrow \mathbf{Z}_{dyn} \setminus \{z_i\}$ 
         $z_j \leftarrow \text{nearestNeighbor}(\mathbf{Z}_{dyn}, z_i)$ 
        if  $c(z_i) \neq c(z_j)$  and  $\|t_c(z_i), t_c(z_j)\| \leq \sigma_{c(z_i)}$  then
            // Merge clusters
             $c(z_i) \leftarrow c(z_j)$ 
             $\mathbf{Z}_{dyn} \leftarrow \mathbf{Z}_{dyn} \cup \{z_i\}$ 
        end
    end
end
end
```

Generative Object Detection/Tracking in 3D Range

Joint Self-Localization/Tracking of Generic Objects in 3D Range

- Both estimation of the trajectory of a sensor and detection and tracking of moving objects for autonomous robots.
- The sole input is a sequence of dense 3D measurements as returned by multi-layer laser scanners or time-of-flight cameras.
- Applicability to any type of environment since specific object models.
- Precise localization in non-flat environments is possible as well as the detection and tracking of e.g. trams or recumbent bicycles.
- 3D shape estimation of moving objects is inherent.

Joint Self-Localization/Tracking of Generic Objects in 3D Range

The pose ρ of the state vector defines the position and the orientation of a track coordinate system w.r.t. the scanner coordinate system. The track appearance is stored as point cloud (violet) with normal vectors and flatness values relative to the track coordinate system.

Joint Self-Localization/Tracking of Generic Objects in 3D Range

Associations between new tracklets (upper) and tracks (lower) are established by overlaying their projections and counting the number of pixels they overlap. Association strengths for moving objects (lower); the edges that are not labeled are associations with the static track (color in gray).

A tracklet is created from each object hypothesis with a minimum size and can be regarded as object hypothesis in the time domain. Tracklets are track hypotheses that, after successful verification, can become tracks.

Joint Self-Localization/Tracking of Generic Objects in 3D Range

Finding Cars, Pedestrians and Bicyclists in 3D Laser

- Segmenting things that could move from 3D laser scans of urban scenes.
- Detect instances of classes of interest in autonomous driving applications - cars, pedestrians and bicyclists - amongst significant background clutter.
- Explore the use of a Euclidean Minimum Spanning Tree for an end-to-end segmentation pipeline and devise a RANSAC-based edge selection criterion.

Finding Cars, Pedestrians and Bicyclists in 3D Laser

Continuous-Time Estimation for Dynamic Obstacle Tracking

- Simultaneously estimate both the obstacle's trajectory and shape.
- By treating obstacle's shape as a “map” in its moving reference frame, formulate obstacle tracking and shape estimation similarly to SLAM.
- A continuous time estimation framework to incorporate sensor data that is collected at a fast rate (e.g., LIDAR).
- Obtain smooth trajectories and crisp point clouds for obstacles.

Continuous-Time Estimation for Dynamic Obstacle Tracking

A high level description of the problem. The obstacle moves along some path $x(t)$. The obstacle is modeled by n_m **model points**. **Observations** such as z_i . Note that each snapshot roughly captures the geometric shape of the obstacle, but is prone to errors due to the obstacle's motion during its collection. Not make the assumption that the points z_i in a single snapshot correspond to the same obstacle pose $x(t)$.

Illustration of our measurement model. The **observation**, is associated with the closest **model point**. The **black points** - other points that make up the obstacle model.

Continuous-Time Estimation for Dynamic Obstacle Tracking

- Simultaneously optimizes for obstacle state over time and the point cloud model for the obstacle through iterative batch optimization.
- In a discrete-time setting, instantiate discrete variables representing the obstacle state at $\mathbf{x}(t_0), \dots, \mathbf{x}(t_{nz})$.
- Treat each observation from the LIDAR sensor to be a separate measurement (as opposed to a snapshot of observations taken at the same time).
- Use continuous time estimation to model the car state as linear comb. of temporal basis functions:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{x}(t) &= [\phi_1(t), \phi_2(t), \dots, \phi_n(t)] \mathbf{c} \\ &= \Phi(t)\mathbf{c}.\end{aligned}$$

- Variables solving for are the vector of weights \mathbf{c} and point cloud model.

Continuous-Time Estimation for Dynamic Obstacle Tracking

The proposed method tracking a person riding a bicycle. Points are colored by the time when they were observed, from blue to yellow.

LiDAR Based Off-road Negative Obstacle Detection

Fusion and Upsampling of EO/LIDAR Data for Multiple Platforms

- (1) Depth Map Projection: The point cloud is projected onto the camera;
- (2) Depth Normalization: Normalizes distances of point cloud points to camera;
- (3) Backfilling: Given the point cloud and projected into the camera, creates a much more dense new point cloud;
- (4) Point Cloud Painting (Inverse of Depth Map Projection): Project point clouds prior projected into the image back out into a new point cloud.

Fusion and Upsampling of EO/LIDAR Data for Multiple Platforms

- (1) The LIDAR point cloud and camera image are fused.
- (2) Scan over the image with windows to backfill (deduce) a point at its center.
- (3) Select support points closest to the camera.
- (4) Select the top N points from the metric.
- (5) Have n points with at least one point in each quadrant.
- (6) Use a linear model to predict the missing point.

Function *Backfill_Window_Scanning*

```

For (  $t = 0$ ;  $t < \text{max\_iteration}$ ;  $t = t + 1$  ) {
  For (  $s = 2$ ;  $s < \text{max\_scales}$ ;  $s = s + 1$  ) {
     $W^x = 2 \cdot (s + 1) - 1$ 
     $W^y = W^x$ 
    For (  $l = 0$ ;  $l < \text{camera\_pixels}$ ;  $l = l + 1$  ) {
      If (  $d_l^o == 0$  ) {
         $\hat{d}_l^o = \text{Backfill\_Location}(l, q_l, W^x, W^y)$ 
        If (  $\hat{d}_l^o > 1$  or  $\hat{d}_l^o < 0$  ) {
           $\hat{d}_l^o = 0$ 
        }
      }
    }
    Else {
       $\hat{d}_l^o = d_l^o$ 
    }
  }
}
For (  $l = 0$ ;  $l < \text{camera\_pixels}$ ;  $l = l + 1$  ) {
   $d_l^o = \hat{d}_l^o$ 
}
}
    
```

Fusion of Velodyne and Camera Data for Scene Parsing

- scene classification and data fusion for 3D-LIDAR scanner (Velodyne) and video camera.
- geometry segmentation for detection of obstacles and ground area from data of the Velodyne.
- the corresponding image collected by video camera is classified patch by patch into more detailed categories.
- The final situation picture is obtained by fusing the classification results of Velodyne data and that of images using the fuzzy logic inference framework.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(a) camera image; (b) 3D pointcloud; (c) ground points; (d) above-ground points; (e) detected bounding boxes of obstacles; (f) pointcloud and detected results; (g) detected results projected to the camera image.

2D/3D Sensor Exploitation and Fusion for Detection

- ❑ object (e.g., vehicles, pedestrians) detection and recognition using a combination of 2D and 3D sensor data.
- ❑ Detection of individual data modalities in parallel, and combined using a fusion scheme.
- ❑ apply deformable part based object detection in the 2D image domain to obtain initial estimates of candidate object regions.
- ❑ 3D blobs (i.e., clusters of 3D points) containing potential objects are extracted from the corresponding input point cloud in an unsupervised manner.
- ❑ A morphological feature set Morph166 is proposed to characterize each of these 3D blobs, and only blobs matched to predefined object models are kept.
- ❑ Based on the individual detections from the aligned 2D and 3D data, further develop a fusion scheme to boost object detection and recognition confidence.

2D/3D Sensor Exploitation and Fusion for Detection

2D/3D Sensor Exploitation and Fusion for Detection

Integrating LIDAR into Stereo for Fast and Improved Disparity Computation

- ❑ Fusion of stereo and LIDARs to compensate for each individual sensor's deficiencies – stereo output is dense, but noisy for large distances, while LIDAR is more accurate, but sparse.
- ❑ Stereo performs poorly on textureless areas and on scenes containing repetitive structures, and the subsequent fusion with LIDAR leads to a degraded estimation of the 3D structure.
- ❑ Integrate LIDAR data directly into the stereo algorithm to reduce false positives while increasing the density of the resulting disparity image on textureless regions.

(a) Raw sparse SRI

(b) Horizontal interpolation

(c) Vertical interpolation

Integrating LIDAR into Stereo for Fast and Improved Disparity Computation

spherical range image (SRI)

(a) Calculate SRI

(b) Apply Min/Max filters

(c) Predict Max/Min disparity images

(d) Calculate reduced DSI

The four steps to generate a reduced Disparity Space Image (DSI).
The color of the spherical range image (SRI) encodes the range.

Integrating LIDAR into Stereo for Fast and Improved Disparity Computation

Disparity images before the refinement step and after for five video frames

Object Detection & Recognition Using Sensor Fusion

- ❑ Forward collision warning system (FCW) detects the dangerous objects in front of the vehicle and warns driver while objects are detected in the warning zone.
- ❑ The stixel-world from stereo camera takes into account that free space in front of vehicles and pedestrians is limited by objects with almost vertical surfaces.
 - ❖ These surfaces are adjacent rectangular sticks of a certain width and height.
- ❑ Detection and tracking phases are performed in the laser space, and object classification methods work in vision space.
- ❑ Bearing of laser scanner is wider than stereo camera, moving object can be found even it does not step into camera detection zone, and it can be tracked for getting actual trajectory by extended Kalman filter (EKF).
- ❑ Apply simultaneous localization, mapping and moving object tracking (SLAMMOT) to distinguish between static and moving objects.

Object Detection & Recognition Using Sensor Fusion

Object Detection & Recognition Using Sensor Fusion

Sensor Fusion for Object Detection & Tracking

Sensor Fusion for Object Detection & Tracking

Frontal Object Perception (FOP) - Moving Object Detection (MOC)

Multi-Sensor Fusion for Moving Object Detection & Tracking

Multi-Sensor Fusion for Moving Object Detection & Tracking

Data association methods for each sensor. (a) Camera: predicted moving object hypotheses are projected into the image space and then associated with a set of detected 'vision targets'. (b) LIDAR: a set of possible 'edge targets' are generated from the predicted moving object hypotheses and then associated with a set of extracted 'edge targets'. (c) Radar: a set of possible 'point targets' are generated from the predicted moving object hypotheses and then associated with a set of detected 'point targets'.

Multi-Sensor Fusion for Moving Object Detection & Tracking

Tracking of a pedestrian (a), Tracking of a bicyclist (b), which was enabled by the vision recognition system.
(c) Mirroring target issue.
(d) Tracking of a vehicle in far distance.
(e)-(h) Vehicle tracking results in various situations.

Fusion of 3D LIDAR and Camera Data for Scene Parsing

- ❑ An approach which performs scene parsing and data fusion for a 3D LIDAR scanner and a video camera.
- ❑ 1. A geometry segmentation algorithm for detection of obstacles and ground areas from data collected by the Velodyne scanner.
- ❑ 2. The corresponding image collected by the video camera is classified patch by patch into more detailed categories.
- ❑ 3. Parsing result of each frame is obtained by fusing the result of Velodyne data and that of image using the fuzzy logic inference framework.
- ❑ 4. Parsing results of consecutive frames smoothed by MRF based temporal fusion.

Fusion of 3D LIDAR and Camera Data for Scene Parsing

Illustration of the proposed sensor fusion approach

Fusion of 3D LIDAR and Camera Data for Scene Parsing

(a)

(b)

Illustration. (a) the camera image. (b) the image with the projected Velodyne points.

Real-time probabilistic fusion of sparse 3D LIDAR - dense stereo

- ❑ 3D perception is often provided by sparse 3D LIDAR scanners, which provide accurate but low density depth maps, and dense stereo approaches, which require significant computational resources for accurate results.
- ❑ A probabilistic method for fusing sparse 3D LIDAR data with stereo images to provide accurate dense depth maps and uncertainty estimates in real-time.

The vehicle (left) is equipped with multiple low-cost 3D LIDAR scanners and a stereo camera. Images from the camera (middle) are fused in real-time with sparse 3D LIDAR points (right, red) to form a dense depth map (right, colored).

Multi-view Random Forest of Local Experts Combining RGB and LIDAR data for Pedestrian Detection

- ❑ Dense depth maps are obtained by first registering the 3D cloud of points captured by a Velodyne sensor with the RGB image captured with the camera, and then interpolating the resulting sparse set of pixels to obtain a dense map where each pixel has an associated depth value.
- ❑ Information provided by each modality can be fused using either an early-fusion scheme, at the feature level, or a late-fusion scheme, at the decision level.

Multi-view Random Forest of Local Experts Combining RGB and LIDAR data for Pedestrian Detection

- ❑ A simple yet effective strategy where the 3D cloud of points is used to obtain a dense depth map is applied.
- ❑ Given that, description techniques, such as HOG and LBP, can be applied in order to obtain a highly distinctive object representation (Note: CNN-based feature learning is SoA).

Dense Depth map generation scheme.

Real-time probabilistic fusion of sparse 3D LIDAR - dense stereo

- ❑ Disparity prior estimated using stereo - LIDAR sensors.
 - ❖ The “Stereo” method uses only sparse points matched from stereo images as support points S ;
 - ❖ The “LIDAR” method uses only 3D LIDAR points as the support points S ;
 - ❖ The “Combined” method uses both the above priors.
- ❑ The Stereo prior provides good coverage except in locations with low texture (e.g. road surfaces);
- ❑ The LIDAR prior is less noisy than the stereo but is sparser and covers less of the overall field of view;
- ❑ The combined prior yields the best of both sensors.

Real-time probabilistic fusion of sparse 3D LIDAR - dense stereo

The Bumblebee XB3 stereo images (top) are fused with sparse 3D LIDAR data from the two Velodyne HDL32-E sensors mounted on the roof (bottom, red points).

Large Scale Localization in Changing Cities with 2D LIDAR

- ❖ A probabilistic experience-based approach to localization with 2D push-broom LIDAR sensors.
- ❖ Build locally metric 3D “swathes” using odometry info.
- ❖ Use GPS as a “weak localizer” to find the most relevant experiences for the current swath, then localize the swath with a robust **sample-based** method.
- ❖ If the current swath is not matched with sufficient accuracy, a new experience is created to capture more environment detail in difficult localization conditions.

Local 3D swath construction from 2D laser scans and vehicle trajectory

Large Scale Localization in Changing Cities with 2D LIDAR

$\mathbf{s}(t) = \{d_1 \dots d_m, r_1 \dots r_m\}$ a 2D LIDAR scan distance reflectance measurement

$$\dot{\hat{\mathbf{x}}}(t) = \hat{\mathbf{v}}(t) \begin{bmatrix} \cos \left(\int_{t_0}^t \hat{w}_z(t) dt \right) \\ \sin \left(\int_{t_0}^t \hat{w}_z(t) dt \right) \\ \sin \left(\int_{t_0}^t \hat{w}_x(t) dt \right) \end{bmatrix}$$

the estimated pose $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)$
by integrating $\dot{\hat{\mathbf{x}}}(t)$
over the period $[t_0, t]$

$\mathbf{Q}_{t_0}^t = g(\hat{\mathbf{v}}, \hat{\mathbf{w}}, \mathbf{S}) \Big|_{t_0}^t$ “Swathe” as local 3D point cloud produced by projecting
2D scans \mathbf{S} along the continuous-time trajectory $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)$

$\mathbf{M} = \{\mathbf{m}^1 \dots \mathbf{m}^n\}$ $\mathbf{m}^i = \langle \mathbf{Q}^i, \mathbf{z}^i \rangle$ Collection of all maps \mathbf{M} (GPS and “swathe”)

$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k = \arg \max_{\mathbf{x}_k} p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{z}_k, \mathbf{M}, \mathbf{Q}_k)$ Localization: estimating the pose of the vehicle

$p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{z}_k, \mathbf{M}, \mathbf{Q}_k) \propto$ The location prior as:

$$p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{z}_k) \prod_i p(\mathbf{Q}_k | \mathbf{x}_k^i, \mathbf{m}^i) \quad p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{z}_k) \propto p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}, \mathbf{u}_k) \prod_i p(\mathbf{z}_k | \mathbf{x}_{k-1}^i)$$

Large Scale Localization in Changing Cities with 2D LIDAR

The prior 3D map (a) and local 3D swathe (b) are both converted to a mesh rasterised to 2D reflectance (c) and height (d) images using a **top-down orthographic projection**. The prior map is rasterised at slightly higher resolution, and the swathe is rasterised at a number of orientation offsets. The tiled cost images (e) are formed by computing the squared difference between reflectances and heights of the map and swathe at a series of additional translational offsets. The height at each pixel of the reflectance images is extracted from the z-buffer. The tiled cost images are reduced to low-resolution cost images (f) and stacked to form a cost volume, and a mean and cov is fit to the volume (g), forming swathe **localisation** estimate.

Lidar Map-Based Vehicle Localization

Road mapping with GraphSLAM

- ❖ A grid cell representation: each cell stores both the average infrared reflectivity and variance;
- ❖ Post-process all trajectories to alignment of overlap areas;
 - GraphSLAM: vehicle poses are linked by inertial and odometry data, and matched sections from log files (loop closure) are linked by alignment offsets (computed by ICP);
 - Unsupervised calibration of laser beams: a response curve for every beam.
- ❖ Calibrate beam intensity to have similar response curves;
- ❖ Project calibrated laser returns from aligned trajectories into a HR probabilistic map;
- ❖ Orthogonal x,y representation with each cell as 15x15cm patch of ground.

Lidar Map-Based Vehicle Localization

Road mapping with GraphSLAM

- ❖ The vehicle transitions through a sequence of poses;
- Poses are linked together through relative odometry data, acquired from the vehicle's inertial guidance system;
- To eliminate the effect of non-stationary objects in the map on subsequent localization, **fits a ground plane** to each laser scan, only retains measurements that coincide with this ground plane;
- For any pose and any (fixed and known) laser angle relative to the vehicle coordinate frame, the expected infrared reflectivity can easily be calculated;
- Model the systematic nature of the noise through a Markov chain, which uses GPS bias term as a latent variable;
- A key step in GraphSLAM, is to first **integrate out** map variables;
- **Map matching** compares local submaps, in order to find the best alignment by identifying overlap.

(a) GPS localization induces ≥ 1 meter of error.

(b) No noticeable error after localization.

Lidar Map-Based Vehicle Localization

Online localization by histogram filter

- ❖ 2-d histogram filter for x,y offsets as likeli. distribut. of vehicle location;
- ❖ Motion update: reduce estimate confidence on motion;
 - A "smooth coordinate" system invariant to GPS jump;
 - Offset from the global coord. system modeled by random walk with Gaussian noise;
 - Practically only consider neighb. cells with distance 2~3 from the cell to be updated;
- ❖ Measurement update: increase confidence in estimate on sensor data;

- Build a rolling grid from accumulated sensor and compare cells btw sensor and map;
- Product over all cells of the probability of observing the sensor data given the map:

$$P(x,y|z,m) = \eta \cdot P(z|x,y,m) \cdot P(x,y)$$

$$P(z|x,y,m) = \prod_{i,j} \exp\left(\frac{-(m_{r(i-x,j-y)} - z_{r(i,j)})^2}{2(m_{\sigma(i-x,j-y)} + z_{\sigma(i,j)})^2}\right)^{\alpha} \quad \alpha > 1$$

$$P(x,y) = \eta \cdot \exp\left(\frac{x^2 + y^2}{-2\sigma_{GPS}^2}\right) \cdot \bar{P}(x,y)$$

- ❖ Most likely estimate

$$x = \frac{\sum_{x,y} P(x,y)^{\alpha} \cdot x}{\sum_{x,y} P(x,y)^{\alpha}} \quad y = \frac{\sum_{x,y} P(x,y)^{\alpha} \cdot y}{\sum_{x,y} P(x,y)^{\alpha}}$$

map cell of GPS offset: $m_{r(i,j)}$

m - map

r - reflectivity mean

σ - reflectivity variance

Lidar Map-Based Vehicle Localization

Online localization by particle filter

- Monte Carlo localizer: The particle filter maintains a 3-d pose vector (x , y , and yaw); roll and pitch are assumed to be sufficiently accurate as is;
- Measurements are integrated in the usual way, by affecting the importance weight that sets the resampling probability;

$$w_t^{[k]} = \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2} (x_t^{[k]} - y_t)^T \Gamma_t^{-1} (x_t^{[k]} - y_t)\right\}$$

Pearson product-moment correlation $\left(\text{corr} \left[\begin{pmatrix} h_1(m, x_t^{[k]}) \\ \vdots \\ h_{180}(m, x_t^{[k]}) \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} z_t^1 \\ \vdots \\ z_t^{180} \end{pmatrix} \right] + 1 \right)$

- As in the mapping step, a local ground plane analysis removes measurement that correspond to non-ground objects;
- A small number of particles are drawn from current GPS pose estimate;
- Normalize the brightness and standard deviation for each individual range scan, and also for the corresponding local map stripes.

LOAM: Lidar Odometry and Mapping

(a) KITTI benchmark

(b)

LOAM: Lidar Odometry and Mapping

Visual Odometry

Lidar Odometry

LOAM: Lidar Odometry and Mapping

Algorithm 1: Lidar Odometry

```

1 input :  $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_k, \mathcal{P}_{k+1}, T_{k+1}^L$  from the last recursion
2 output :  $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_{k+1}$ , newly computed  $T_{k+1}^L$ 
3 begin
4   if at the beginning of a sweep then
5      $T_{k+1}^L \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ ;
6   end
7   Detect edge points and planar points in  $\mathcal{P}_{k+1}$ , put the points in
8    $\mathcal{E}_{k+1}$  and  $\mathcal{H}_{k+1}$ , respectively;
9   for a number of iterations do
10    for each edge point in  $\mathcal{E}_{k+1}$  do
11      Find an edge line as the correspondence, then compute
12      point to line distance based on (9) and stack the equation
13      to (11);
14    end
15    for each planar point in  $\mathcal{H}_{k+1}$  do
16      Find a planar patch as the correspondence, then compute
17      point to plane distance based on (10) and stack the
18      equation to (11);
19    end
20    Compute a bisquare weight for each row of (11);
21    Update  $T_{k+1}^L$  for a nonlinear iteration based on (12);
22    if the nonlinear optimization converges then
23      Break;
24    end
25  end
26  if at the end of a sweep then
27    Reproject each point in  $\mathcal{P}_{k+1}$  to  $t_{k+2}$  and form  $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_{k+1}$ ;
28    Return  $T_{k+1}^L$  and  $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_{k+1}$ ;
29  end
30 else
31   Return  $T_{k+1}^L$ ;
32 end

```


Fig. Illustration of mapping process. The blue colored curve represents the lidar pose on the map, T_k^W , generated by the mapping algorithm at sweep k . The orange color curve indicates the lidar motion during sweep $k+1$, T_{k+1}^L , computed by the odometry algorithm. With T_k^W and T_{k+1}^L , the undistorted point cloud published by the odometry algorithm is projected onto the map, denoted as \bar{Q}_{k+1} (the green colored line segments), and matched with the existing cloud on the map, Q_k (the black colored line segments).

Fig. Integration of pose transforms. The blue colored region illustrates the lidar pose from the mapping algorithm, T_k^W , generated once per sweep. The orange colored region is the lidar motion within the current sweep, T_{k+1}^L , computed by the odometry algorithm. The motion estimation of the lidar is the combination of the two transforms, at the same frequency as T_{k+1}^L .

Visual-LiDAR Odometry + 3D IMU

Visual+LiDAR Mapping + GPS/INS

Visual+LiDAR Mapping + GPS/INS

Data Acquisition

LIDAR IMU GNSS Vision

HD: Stored Raw Sensor Data

IMU & GNSS Sensor Trajectory Optimization

Initial Smoothed IMU Trajectory

Feature Extraction, Tracking, & Identification

Feature Measurements in Sensor Frames

LIDAR, Vision, GNSS, IMU Feature Map & Trajectory Optimization

Feature Locations in Geodetic Frame

Roadway Feature GIS Database

Offline Map Processing

Finding Lanes and Curves

Visual+LiDAR Mapping + GPS/INS

Lane Departure Warning

Lane Edge Extraction and Curve Estimation

- Ground plane image projection from measurements
- Output: intensity as a function of position
- Curve detection using projected vehicle trajectory on ground plane images
- Output: Curves composed of a set of sequential 3D positions in world frame

Curve Overspeed Warning

Curve Parameterization

- Primary input: curves from previous step
- Step: Curve Fitting
- Output: roadway curve format for GIS

Velodyne SLAM

Pre-Processing:

- range measurement R_i : $i \mapsto r$
- point coordinates \vec{P}_i : $i \mapsto (x, y, z)^T$
- distance vector $\vec{D}_{i,j} = \vec{P}_j - \vec{P}_i$
- linkage value $L_{i,j}$: $i, j \mapsto l$
- normal vector \vec{N}_i : $i \mapsto (n_x, n_y, n_z)^T$
- normal confidence C_i : $i \mapsto c$

Velodyne SLAM

Localization:

ICP

$$E(v) = \sum_{i \in \text{scan}} (\vec{n}_{\text{NN}(i)}^T (\mathbf{T}(\vec{P}_i, v) - \vec{p}_{\text{NN}(i)}))^2$$

Deskewing:

Mapping:

a map is a loose collection of surfaces in a world reference frame

The map is stored in a 3D grid structure with each cell containing maximally one surface according to its 3D position. The grid resolution hence defines the level of detail of the map.

$$\vec{P}'_i(a) = \vec{P}_i + a \cdot \vec{N}_i$$
$$E_{S_i}(a) = \sum_{j \in \text{kNN}(S_i)} w_{ij} (\vec{n}_j^T (\vec{P}'_i(a) - \vec{p}_j))^2$$
$$w_{ij} = C_i c_j \vec{N}_i^T \vec{n}_j$$

Map Refinement:

$$E_{s_i}(a) = \sum_{j \in \text{kNN}(s_i)} w_{ij} (\vec{n}_j^T (\vec{p}'_i(a) - \vec{o}_j))^2$$
$$w_{ij} = c_i c_j \vec{n}_i^T \vec{n}_j$$

The idea for refinement is similar to the adaptation step.

Model Based Vehicle Detection & Tracking

Ground Removal

- 3d data scan: slice space directly above ground and up to 2m high;
- Objects elevated more than 2m above ground – not obstacles;
 - ✓ Low obstacles such as curbs excluded from virtual scans;
- Build a 3d grid in spherical coordinates, compute the median range of sensor data falling within each spherical grid cell;
- “Virtual ray” as the cone from the grid origin to the obstacle point;
- Select a single slice of vertical angles from the spherical grid, from the lowest to the highest;
- Simple thresholding to classify ground sensor data;
 - ✓ Local ground elevation estimation;
 - ✓ Classify remaining non-ground sensor data:
 - Low, medium and high obstacles;
 - ✓ Filter out (medium): birds, insects and occasional from cat-eye reflectors.

Model Based Vehicle Detection & Tracking

Sensor Data: Virtual Scan

- ❑ A grid in polar coord.s: subdivide 360° into angular grid cells (cone);
- ❑ Information: free, occupied or occluded(note: angular resolution);
- ❑ Allow constant time look-up for any given point in the space;
- ❑ Measurement model: given pose X , geometry G , virtual scan Z

$$p(Z|G, X) = \prod_{i=1}^N p(z_i|G, X) = \eta_i \exp\left(-\frac{c_i^2}{2\sigma_i^2}\right)$$

- ❑ Assume independence of measurements along each ray.

Model Based Vehicle Detection & Tracking

Tracking by ADH(Annealed Dynamic Histogram)

- A grid-based method to sample velocities from the state space;
- Efficient sample from a large grid in real time by a way called Annealed Dynamic Histograms (ADH);
 - Sampling with a coarse grid, then for each sample, compute the probab. of the state using the DBN model;
 - Then subdivide some of grid cells to refine the distribution;
 - In practice, compute by a kd-tree to look-up NN in the grid cell.
- Use the latent surface in the measurement model to guide how to select model para;
- A set of points is sampled independently from the surface of the object;
- Multi modal: color, shape and motion;

$$p(z_t | x_t, z_{t-1}) = \int \int p(z_t, s_t, s_{t-1} | x_t, z_{t-1}) ds_{t-1} ds_t$$

$$p(s_{t,j} | s_{t-1}) = \eta(p(s_{t,j} | s_{t-1}, V) + k_3) \mathcal{N}(s_{t-1,i}, \Sigma_r)$$

$$\begin{aligned} p(z_t, s_t, s_{t-1} | x_t, z_{t-1}) \\ &= p(z_t | s_t, x_t) p(s_t | s_{t-1}) p(s_{t-1} | z_{t-1}) \\ &= \eta p(z_t | s_t, x_t) p(s_t | s_{t-1}) p(z_{t-1} | s_{t-1}) p(s_{t-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} p(z_t | x_t, z_{t-1}) \text{ nearest predicted points from motion} \\ &= \eta \left(\prod_{z_j \in z_t} \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} (z_j - \bar{z}_i)^T \Sigma^{-1} (z_j - \bar{z}_i) \right) + k \right) \end{aligned}$$

Model Based Vehicle Detection & Tracking

Track-based Classification

- ❑ Solve a multiclass problem: car, pedestrian, bicyclist, or background;
- ❑ Stanford Track Collection (STC): 1.3 million labeled segmented objects across roughly 14,000 tracks, a max range of 70m and mean range of 30m;
- ❑ Descriptors for classifiers:
 - ❖ Segment descriptor: oriented bounding box size, 4 different parameterizations of spin images, 24 different HoG from virtual orthographic camera intensity images;
 - ✓ Spin images based on the vertical axis, “whitened”, i.e. scaled to have zero mean and unit variance;
 - ❖ Holistic descriptor: max and mean speed, max and mean acceleration, max angular velocity, segment descriptors;
- ❑ Track-based classifier within a boosting framework:
 - ❖ Segment classifier: given appearance of an object at a point in time;
 - ❖ Holistic classifier: given appearance of speed, acceleration ,other properties as a whole;
 - ❖ A 1-vs-all scheme with GentleBoost and JointBoost.
- ❑ The augmented discrete Bayes filter (ADBF)
 - ❖ Equivalent to logistic regression on the output of the holistic and segment classifiers with an intercept term (the variable length of tracks);

LiDAR-based Tracking Using RNN

Leverage a RNN to effectively reveal occluded parts of a scene by learning to track objects from raw sensor data – thereby effectively reversing the sensing process.

Filtering using a RNN.

The 4-layer RNN used for the system. Visible objects are detected in Encoder and fed into Belief tracker to update belief \mathcal{B}_t for scene deocclusion in Decoder.

End-to-End Tracking and Semantic Segmentation by RNNs with LiDAR

- The stream of raw sensor data is filtered by a RNN and produces classification of both directly visible and occluded space into one of several semantic classes;
 - The network is trained to predict output consistent with future inputs;
 - This allows training without the need of ground-truth information of the full, unoccluded scene;
 - First the network learns how to track by predicting correct occupancy using large amounts of unlabelled data, then a small set of labelled data is used to induce semantic classification (inductive transfer).

End-to-End Tracking and Semantic Segmentation by RNNs with LiDAR

Classical multi-stage pipeline

End-to-end pipeline

End-to-End Tracking and Semantic Segmentation by RNNs with LiDAR

Training of the RNN to produce both space occupancy y_t and semantic labels c_t .

End-to-End Tracking and Semantic Segmentation by RNNs with LiDAR

In the proposed structure, it features dilated convolution, enhanced static and dynamic memory capabilities whereas producing information of both cell occupancy and its semantic class.

$$f_t = \sigma(W_{xz} * x_t + W_{hz} * h_{t-1} + b_z),$$

$$r_t = \sigma(W_{xr} * x_t + W_{hr} * h_{t-1} + b_r),$$

$$\bar{h}_t = \tanh(W_{xh} * x_t + r_t \circ W_{hh} * h_{t-1} + b_h),$$

$$h_t = f_t \circ h_{t-1} + (1 - f_t) \circ \bar{h}_t.$$

A convolutional variant of GRUs

Unsupervised Feature Learning for Classification of Outdoor 3D Scans

PCA interpolation process

- A method for formatting segmented regions of Velodyne scans into regularly sampled depth images.
- This reformatting allows to leverage existing feature learning techniques and apply them to Velodyne data.
- Features are learnt on the raw Velodyne range images and evaluated on the interpolated depth images.
- Classification performance produced by learnt features compare favorably against classifiers based on pre-defined 3D features such as the Spin Images or other alternatives.

(b) Range Image non-returns

Unsupervised Feature Learning for Classification of Outdoor 3D Scans

```

Input : PointCloud, ImageResolution,  $R_{PCA}$ ,  $t$ 
Output: NormalizedDepthImage
for  $P \in \textit{PointCloud}$  do
    | neighbours = Sphere(  $P$ ,  $R_{PCA}$ )
    |  $\mu_P, \Sigma_P, \Lambda_P = \text{PCA}(\text{neighbours})$ 
end
ImagePlane =
    SamplingPlane(PointCloud)
for  $i, j \in \textit{ImagePlane}$  do
    |  $\textit{Ray} = \text{NormVector}(i, j)$ 
    |  $p = \arg \max_p \mathcal{N}(p; \mu, \Sigma, \Lambda)$  s.t.  $p \in \textit{Ray}$ 
    | if  $\mathcal{N}(p; \mu_P, \Sigma, \Lambda) > t$  then
    | |  $\textit{DepthImage}[i, j] = p$ 
    | | else
    | |  $\textit{DepthImage}[i, j] = 0$ 
    | | end
    | end
NormalizedDepthImage =
    NormalizeImage(DepthImage)
return NormalizedDepthImage

```

Algorithm 1: Point Projection

Table 1: Variables used in Algorithm 1

P	An input point cloud.
t	Threshold for depth interpolation.
<i>Ray</i>	A ray normal to the Image plane, passing through a point cloud.
p	A point on the line L .
R_{PCA}	PCA is computed on a spherical region of points at this radii.

The sampling process represents local regions as Gaussians. These regions are then projected onto an image plane and interpolated to form a regular grid of depth values. Depth values are normalized to the range [0.5, 1] and free space is set to 0, (lines 17 and 13 of Algorithm 1). It is built by applying PCA on spherical regions of radius about each point on the object scan (line 1-3 in Algorithm 1). A plane is then positioned at the centroid of the object scan, such that its surface normal is the ray connecting the centre of the camera to the centre of mass of the object (Algorithm 1 line 6). This plane forms the image plane and per-pixel depth values are got by extruding a 3D line from each pixel out into the Gaussian surface model (Algorithm 1 line 8).

Unsupervised Feature Learning for Classification of Outdoor 3D Scans

- An illustration of the line image feature computed on the corner of a car, which has been partly occluded by a trunk.
- Status of each line, and depth of surface intercept, is shown on the left.
- The point cloud is colored by surface normals for visualization.

Unsupervised Feature Learning for Classification of Outdoor 3D Scans

Illustration of the Spin Image feature.

Examples of labeled point clouds. Labels clockwise from the top: car, person, tree, lights, sign, pole, pillar, wall, truck, bus, 4wd.

Vehicle Detection from 3D Lidar Using FCN

- ❑ Point clouds from a Velodyne scan can be roughly projected and discretized into a 2D point map;
- ❑ The projected point map analogous to cylindrical images;

bounding box corner $c_p = (x_c, y_c, z_c)$ is thus transformed as:

$$c'_p = R^T(c_p - p) \quad (3)$$

- ❑ Encode the bounding box corner of the vehicle (8 corners as 24-d);

$$b'_p = (c'_{p,1}, c'_{p,2}, \dots, c'_{p,8})^T$$

- ❑ It consists of one objectness classification branch and one bounding box regression branch.

Vehicle Detection from 3D Lidar Using FCN

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(a) The input point map, with the d channel visualized. (b) The output confidence map of the objectness branch. (c) Bounding box candidates corresponding to all points predicted as positive, i.e. high confidence points in (b). (d) Remaining bounding boxes after non-max suppression.

VoxNet: 3D CNN for Object Recognition

- ❑ Integrate a volumetric Occupancy Grid representation with a supervised 3D CNN;
- ❑ The input is a point cloud segment, originating from segmentation, or a “sliding box” if running detection;
- ❑ The task is to predict object class label for the segment.

LIDAR-based 3D Object Perception

Occupancy grid

Querying data from the occupancy grid

- A 2.5-D ego-centered occupancy grid of 100m x 100m, each cell covering a small ground patch of 0.15m x 0.15m;
 - Each cell stores a value expressing how occupied that cell is by an obstacle;
 - Inertially motion compensate the LIDAR scan (IMU/odometry info.);
 - Each cell's value is the max abs. diff. in z-coord.s of all points in the respective grid cell;
 - When a grid cell is hit by a laser beam and its occupancy value is updated, store the laser read at the cell;
- Segmentation: Find connected components of grid cells;
- Classification: SVM;
 - Augment the grid with a facility to answer queries for data as arbitrary polygons, with vertices defined in the ego coord. system;
 - Given a query, transform vertex coord.s from ego to grid and split polygon into triangles;
 - Issue the triangle scan conversion, such that every cell in the orig. polygon will be visited;
 - Answering the query: collecting all the laser reads stored at the visited cells;
 - Object level and hist.s of point level features (by Angelov and Lalonde): 28-d vector.

LIDAR-based 3D Object Perception

Positive examples (top 4 rows) and negative examples (bottom 4 rows).

Occupancy grid with objects segmentation

Tracking with position and velocity estimates

Multi-View 3D Object Detection Network for Autonomous Driving

- ❑ Multi-View 3D networks (MV3D), a sensory-fusion framework that takes both LIDAR point cloud and RGB images as input and predicts oriented 3D b boxes.
- ❑ Composed of 2 subnetworks: one for 3D object proposal generation, one for multi-view feature fusion.
- ❑ The proposal network generates 3D candidate boxes from bird's eye view representation of 3D point cloud.
- ❑ A deep fusion scheme to combine region-wise features from multiple views and enable interactions btw intermediate layers of different paths.

Multi-View 3D Object Detection Network for Autonomous Driving

Multi-View 3D Object Detection Network for Autonomous Driving

Height Maps

Density

Intensity

(a) Bird's eye view features

Height

Distance

Intensity

(b) Front view features

(c) RGB image

$$c = \lfloor \text{atan2}(y, x) / \Delta\theta \rfloor$$

$$r = \lfloor \text{atan2}(z, \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}) / \Delta\phi \rfloor,$$

Input features of the MV3D network.

Multi-View 3D Object Detection Network for Autonomous Driving

Training strategy for the Region-based Fusion Network: During training, the bottom 3 paths and losses are added to regularize the network. The auxiliary layers share weights with the corresponding layers in the main network.

LiDAR Segmentation (Clustering)

LiDAR Segmentation (Clustering)

- **Surface-based** segmentation approaches

- Edge-based [Boo, SD01]
- Curvature-based [BJ88, HJJ96, PBJ98]
- Scanline grouping [JB94, KMK03]
- Geometric primitives [MLM01, BGo6, SWK07]
- Smooth regions [RHVo6, RMB08]

- **Norm vector:**

- Optimization-based;
$$\min_{n_i} J(p_i, Q_i, n_i)$$
- Averaging;
$$n_i = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k w_j \frac{([q_{i,j} - p_i] \times [q_{i,j+1} - p_i])}{|[q_{i,j} - p_i] \times [q_{i,j+1} - p_i]|}$$
- Graph: K-NN and Delaunay triangulation;

- **Curvature values;**

- Surface variation.

$$\sigma_{sv} = \frac{3\sigma_3}{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3}, \quad \sigma_1 > \sigma_2 > \sigma_3$$

LiDAR Segmentation (Clustering)

- **Occlusion:**
 - Model-free (hole filling) [DF02, W003, BPBo6];
 - Model-based (object recognition) [Boo, BI00, TBo7];
- Occlusions cause over-segmentation;
- Reason about plausibility of occlusion [DF02];
- Merging over-segmented surfaces
 - Identify candidate surfaces by 4 distance measures;
 - Identify pairs of boundary points on each segment;
- Check connecting lines for occlusion
 - Create an omnidirectional range image (ORI) for all points observed from one view point;
 - For each boundary line check the corresponding line in the image for occlusion;

LiDAR Segmentation (Clustering)

- Classification: use the segmented surfaces as an abstract representation for detecting objects;
- Segment features:
 - Centroid, normal vector, surface variation, axis-aligned bounding box, convex hull etc.
- Train primitive classifiers for parts
- Find structure in neighboring classified segments
 - Convert neighborhood relationship to graph
 - Complete/sub-graph matching
 - Part-based approaches
- Train with object CAD models or real 3-d point cloud data?

LiDAR Graph-based Segmentation

- Separation from the ground: dimension reduction;
 - Projection to a ground plane;
 - Projection to a virtual image plane to a so-called *range image*;
- Graph methods:
 - Neighborhood graph construction;
 - Attribute calculation;
 - Segmentation: based on local convexity;

$$\text{grow}(s_i, s_j) = \text{lc}(s_i, s_j) \vee [(|z_{\vec{n}_i}| < \epsilon_3) \wedge (|z_{\vec{n}_j}| < \epsilon_3)] \quad 0 \leq \epsilon_3 \leq 1$$

$$\text{lc}(s_i, s_j) = \begin{cases} \text{true} & [(\vec{n}_i \cdot \vec{d}_{ij} \leq \|\vec{d}_{ij}\| \cdot \cos(\frac{\pi}{2} - \epsilon_1)) \\ & \wedge (\vec{n}_j \cdot \vec{d}_{ji} \leq \|\vec{d}_{ji}\| \cdot \cos(\frac{\pi}{2} - \epsilon_1))] \\ & \vee [\vec{n}_i \cdot \vec{n}_j \geq 1 - \|\vec{d}_{ij}\| \cdot \cos(\frac{\pi}{2} - \epsilon_2)] \\ \text{false} & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

- 1) Select a seed node randomly
- 2) Grow the segment until no more nodes are added
- 3) Delete the segment from the graph

LiDAR Graph-based Segmentation

3D point cloud (blueness as height) -> Neighborhood Graph

->Normal vectors

->Segmentation

Concave street in a tunnel

-> Convex gateway

->3D point cloud (Blue as height, red as depth) ->Segments

LiDAR Graph-based Segmentation

Real-time LiDAR Segmentation & Classification

How to fill the Diff image from the Min and Max images?

1. For location of the window $\langle i,j \rangle$ find the min pixel value P_{min} in the Min image.
2. Mark Diff image location $\langle i,j \rangle$ as 255 if $\text{abs}(P_{min} - P_{max}(i,j)) \geq T$ and the cell is not empty
3. Move window to the next location.

grid processing

Real-time LiDAR Segmentation & Classification

filling the Min and Max images of rectangular grid

Segmentation with the rectangular grid

Real-time LiDAR Segmentation & Classification

Filling the Min and Max images for the radial grid

Segmentation with the radial grid

Lidar-based Segmentation and Classification

- LiDAR data preprocessing: road direction;
- Segmentation: surface growing (region growing in 2-d image), ground points removal, CCA;
- Feature extraction: shape, contextual, eigenvalue.
- Classification: segment-based.

Lidar-based Segmentation and Classification

1 Laser data preprocessing

2 Segmentation

3 Feature extraction

4 Classification

LiDAR-based Ground Segmentation

- Method categories:
 1. **Elevation map** methods: 3D point cloud is projected onto a horizontal plane with an elevation map to reduce dimensionality, which is commonly classified as 2.5D grid model;
 - Problem: Under-segmentation, hard to select the appropriate threshold for sloped ground with vegetation, hills, or curbs in outdoor environments.
 2. **Ground modeling** methods: A line-based ground model for every sector in polar grid map;
 3. **Relationship between adjacent points**: Extract local point features from the normal vectors and then apply Euclidean clustering and region growing;
 4. MRF-based methods: Gaussian Mixture Models.

LiDAR-based Ground Segmentation

LiDAR+Camera-based Scene Parsing

- ❑ Local 3D geometrical features extracted from subsets of point clouds are classified by trained boosted decision trees and then corresponding image segments are labeled with semantic classes e.g. buildings, road, sky etc.
- ❑ It is robust to varying imaging conditions such as lighting and urban structures.

LiDAR+Camera-based Scene Parsing

- ❑ Every collection of 3D points is assumed to be sampled from a visible planar 3D object i.e. patch and corresponding 2D projections are confined within a homogenous region i.e. superpixels (SPs) of the image;
- ❑ The 3D-2D projection between patches and SPs is straightforward for known geometrical configurations to deal with outlier 3D points.

LiDAR+Camera-based Scene Parsing

The **top** image shows 3D LiDAR point cloud in NED system. The occluded points in the one bystreet are shown in a green circle. The **bottom** image illustrates camera view of scene, occluded points in the bystreet located in the red square (corresponding to red line in top image) will be deleted.

Test Image

Ground truth

Parsing Result

Fusion Based Holistic Road Scene Understanding

(a) Image (b) Produced objects hypotheses (c) Segmentation result (d) Category labeling result

Ground Sky Vehicle Cyclist Pedestrian Sitter Pole Greenbelt Background

- ❑ An approach that jointly tackles object-level image segmentation and semantic region labeling within a CRF.
- ❑ First generate semantic object hypotheses by clustering 3D points, learning their prior appearance models, and using a deep learning method for reasoning their semantic categories.
- ❑ The learned priors, together with spatial and geometric contexts, are incorporated in CRF.
- ❑ Visual and range data are fused thoroughly, and coupled segmentation and semantic labeling is inferred via Graph Cuts.

Fusion Based Holistic Road Scene Understanding

(a) 3D point cloud

(b) Image

(c) Upsampled dense depth map

(d) 3D clusters and bounding boxes

(e) Object candidates on the image

(f) Object-level segmentation

(g) Object detection on 3D points

(h) Object detection on the image

(i) Semantic region labeling

3D point cloud (a), image (b), depth map (c), object hypotheses (d), object candidates (e), image segment. (f), object detection on the image(h), object detection on the point cloud (g) semantic region labeling (i).

Fusion Based Holistic Road Scene Understanding

The CRF model: two hidden layers of random variables associated with each pixel, one for object-level segmentation and the other for semantic region labeling. The CRF model integrates the observed features together with the seeds, pivoted hard constraints and the geometric contextual information to infer the joint problem.

Thanks!